

Algebraic Cyclic, Flat and Cornered Striped Magic Squares for Even Orders from 4 to 20

The whole work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17058>

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Abstract

This work brings **algebraic striped** magic squares for even orders from 4 to 20 for the **reduced entries**. By **reduced or less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These entries are non-sequential positive and negative numbers. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of the entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe decimal or fractional values of the entries depending on the types of magic squares. This work is on **double-digit** or **double-layer bordered** and **cornered** magic squares. In case of **double-digit**, we have two different ways of writing. One is **cyclic-type** and the another is **flat-type**. In case of **cyclic-type**, each layer has four equal sums **magic rectangles** and in case of **flat-type**, we have two big and two small **magic rectangles**. Including the **corner-type**, there are three different types of magic squares for each order are studied in this work. Whole the work in in terms of equal **width** magic rectangles calling as **striped** magic squares. For the first time, in the literature of magic squares, the idea of **double-digit bordered** magic squares for sequential number entries is studied by the author [31]. This work is for non-sequential entries. Moreover, in this work the magic rectangles are considered as **cyclic, flat or cornered**. For similar kind of work for different orders in different styles and designs, the readers are suggested to see author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21].

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1 Introduction

This work brings **algebraic striped** magic squares for even orders from 4 to 20 for the **reduced entries**. By **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These entries are non-sequential positive and negative numbers. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe decimal or fractional values of the entries depending on the types of magic squares. The work **double-digit** or **double-layer bordered** and **cornered** magic squares. In case of **double-digit**, we have two different ways of writing. One is **cyclic-type** and another is **flat-type**. In case of **cyclic-type**, each layer has four equal sums magic rectangles and in case of **flat-type**, we have two big and two small magic rectangles in each layer. Including the **corner-type**, we have each order in three different types of magic squares.

We know that magic sum of a magic square of order n having 1 to n^2 number of entries is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}$$

In this work the entries are written as variables and their combinations. Instead of sequential entries, we have non-sequential entries. These can be positive, negative or decimal numbers.

This work brings **double-digit** or **double-layer algebraic striped** magic squares of even orders from 4 to 20 for reduced entries. Sometimes, these types of magic squares, we call as **self-made**, because they are complete in themselves. Just choose the entries and magic sum, we always get a magic square.

Whole the work in terms of equal width magic rectangles calling **striped** magic squares. The idea of **double-digit** for magic squares for sequential number entries studied by the author [31] for the first time. This work is for non-sequential entries. Moreover, we have considered the magic rectangles in a cyclic, flat or cornered way. For similar kind of work for different orders in different styles and ways, the readers are suggested to see author's work [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. For **double-digit** work for **sequential** entries refer [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31].

2 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares

The section bring results and examples of **reduced entries algebraic striped** magic squares complete in itself for even orders from 4 to 20. These are of three types: **cyclic-type**, **flat-type** and **corner-type**. In case of orders 4 and 6, we don't have much possibilities.

2.1 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Square of Order 4

Result 2.1. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 4 is given by*

$a_4 - 2a_2 - a_3 + 2m - a_1$	a_1	a_2	$a_2 + a_3 - a_4$
$a_1 - a_4 + 2a_2 + a_3 - m$	$m - a_1$	$m - a_2$	$a_4 - a_2 - a_3 + m$
a_3	a_4	$a_1 - a_4 + a_2$	$2m - a_3 - a_1 - a_2$
$m - a_3$	$m - a_4$	$m - a_1 + a_4 - a_2$	$a_3 + a_1 + a_2 - m$
$a_4 - 2a_2 - a_3 + 2m - a_1$	$a_1 - a_4 + 2a_2 + a_3 - m$	a_3	$m - a_3$
a_1	$m - a_1$	a_4	$m - a_4$
a_2	$m - a_2$	$a_1 - a_4 + a_2$	$m - a_1 + a_4 - a_2$
$a_2 + a_3 - a_4$	$a_4 - a_2 - a_3 + m$	$2m - a_3 - a_1 - a_2$	$a_3 + a_1 + a_2 - m$

• Details

Above there are two ways of representing **algebraic striped** magic square of order 4 where the strips are either in a horizontal way or in a vertical way. In both the situations, the result is always a magic square. Here we use only 4 entries instead of 16, where m is the width of the magic rectangle. In this case the magic sum is $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$. See below some examples:

Example 2.1. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 4 based on Result 2.1 are given by

4	mgc			44		4	mgc			44	
	11	10	13	10	44		11	11	16	6	44
	11	12	9	12	44		10	12	19	3	44
	16	19	4	5	44		13	9	4	18	44
	6	3	18	17	44		10	12	5	17	44
	44	44	44	44	44		44	44	44	44	44
4	mgc			54		4	mgc			54	
	21	10	13	10	54		21	6	16	11	54
	6	17	14	17	54		10	17	19	8	54
	16	19	4	15	54		13	14	4	23	54
	11	8	23	12	54		10	17	15	12	54
	54	54	54	54	54		54	54	54	54	54

In the first case, the magic sum is $S_{4 \times 4} := 44, m := 22$. In the second case, the magic sum is $S_{4 \times 4} := 54, m := 27$.

2.2 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 6

Below are two different ways of writing magic square of order 6.

Result 2.2. An algebraic striped magic square of order 6 is given by

$a_4 - 2a_2 - a_3 + 2m - a_1$	a_1	a_2	$a_2 + a_3 - a_4$	a_5	$m - a_5$
$a_1 - a_4 + 2a_2 + a_3 - m$	$m - a_1$	$m - a_2$	$a_4 - a_2 - a_3 + m$	a_6	$m - a_6$
a_3	a_4	$a_1 - a_4 + a_2$	$2m - a_3 - a_1 - a_2$	a_7	$m - a_7$
$m - a_3$	$m - a_4$	$m - a_1 + a_4 - a_2$	$a_3 + a_1 + a_2 - m$	$2m - a_5 - a_6 - a_7$	$a_5 + a_6 + a_7 - m$
$3m - a_5 + a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - a_8$	$m - a_8$	$m - a_9$	$a_5 - a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + 2a_8 + a_9 + 2a_{10} - 4m$	$m - a_{10}$	$m - a_{10}$
$a_5 - a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + a_8 - 2m$	a_8	a_9	$5m - a_5 + a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - 2a_8 - a_9 - 2a_{10}$	a_{10}	a_{10}

● **Details**

It is an **algebraic cornered-type striped** magic square of order 6, where there is a magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner formed by two equal sums strips of order 2×4 . The magic sum of order 6 is $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangles. Whole the magic square of order 6 is formed by 3 strips of order 2×4 and one strip of order 2×6 . See below few examples:

Example 2.2. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 6 based on Result 2.2 are given by

6	mgc					63	6	mgc						84			
		11	10	11	10	14	7	63			25	10	11	10	14	14	84
		10	11	10	11	15	6	63			3	18	17	18	15	13	84
		12	13	8	9	16	5	63			12	13	8	23	16	12	84
		9	8	13	12	-3	24	63			16	15	20	5	11	17	84
		6	4	3	46	2	2	63			27	11	10	18	9	9	84
		15	17	18	-25	19	19	63			1	17	18	10	19	19	84
		63	63	63	63	63	63	63			84	84	84	84	84	84	84
6	mgc					63	6	mgc						84			
		11	10	12	9	14	7	63			25	3	12	16	14	14	84
		10	11	13	8	15	6	63			10	18	13	15	15	13	84
		11	10	8	13	16	5	63			11	17	8	20	16	12	84
		10	11	9	12	-3	24	63			10	18	23	5	11	17	84
		6	4	3	46	2	2	63			27	11	10	18	9	9	84
		15	17	18	-25	19	19	63			1	17	18	10	19	19	84
		63	63	63	63	63	63	63			84	84	84	84	84	84	84

Above there are two ways of writing the algebraic striped magic square of order 6. The first way is of **corner-type** while the second one **normal type**. In both the cases the magic sums are:

(i) First case:

- First Example: $S_{6 \times 6} := 63, S_{4 \times 4} := 42$ and $m := 21$.
- Second Example: $S_{6 \times 6} := 84, S_{4 \times 4} := 56$ and $m := 28$.

(ii) Second case:

- First Example: $S_{6 \times 6} := 63, S_{4 \times 4} := 42$ and $m := 21$.
- Second Example: $S_{6 \times 6} := 84, S_{4 \times 4} := 56$ and $m := 28$.

Result 2.3. An algebraic striped magic square of order 6 is given by

$3*m-a2-a3-a1-a5-a4$	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5
$a1+a5+a4+a2+a3-2*m$	m-a1	m-a2	m-a3	m-a4	m-a5
a6	a7	a8	$a8+3*m-2*a1+a12-a13-a2-a3-a5-a4$	$a5+a4+2*a1-a12+a13+a2+a3-a9-a6-a7-2*a8$	a9
m-a6	m-a7	m-a8	$a5+a4-a8+2*a1-a12+a13+a2+a3-2*m$	$m+a6+a7+2*a8-a5-a4-2*a1+a12-a13-a2-a3+a9$	m-a9
$3*m-2*a1-2*a4+a10+a12-a13-a2-a3$	a10	$2*a1+2*a4-2*a10-2*a12+a2+a3-a11$	a11	a12	a13
$2*a1+2*a4-a10-a12+a13+a2+a3-2*m$	m-a10	$m-2*a1-2*a4+2*a10+2*a12-a2-a3+a11$	m-a11	m-a12	m-a13

• **Details**

It is an *algebraic cornered-type striped* magic square of order 6 composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 . The magic sum of order 6 is $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangles. See below few examples:

Example 2.3. Below are two examples of *algebraic striped* magic square of order 6 based on Result 2.2 are given by

6	mgc						162	6	mgc							162
		82	10	13	16	19	22			82	-28	25	29	109	-55	162
		-28	44	41	38	35	32			10	44	28	26	37	17	162
		25	28	31	100	-56	34			13	41	31	23	-113	167	162
		29	26	23	-46	110	20			16	38	100	-46	40	14	162
		109	37	-113	40	43	46			19	35	-56	110	43	11	162
		-55	17	167	14	11	8			22	32	34	20	46	8	162
		162	162	162	162	162	162			162	162	162	162	162	162	162
6	mgc						147	6	mgc							147
		67	10	13	16	19	22			67	-18	25	24	94	-45	147
		-18	39	36	33	30	27			10	39	28	21	37	12	147
		25	28	31	85	-56	34			13	36	31	18	-113	162	147
		24	21	18	-36	105	15			16	33	85	-36	40	9	147
		94	37	-113	40	43	46			19	30	-56	105	43	6	147
		-45	12	162	9	6	3			22	27	34	15	46	3	147
		147	147	147	147	147	147			147	147	147	147	147	147	147

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 162, MR_{2 \times 6} := 54 \times 162$ and $m := 54$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 147, MR_{2 \times 6} := 49 \times 147$ and $m := 49$.

2.3 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 8

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 8, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.3.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.4. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 8 in cyclic way is given by*

a7	a8	a9	a10	a11	$3^*m-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11$	m-a12	a12
m-a7	m-a8	m-a9	m-a10	m-a11	$a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-2^*m$	m-a13	a13
$(3/2)^*2^*m-a24-a23-a22-a21+a12-a13$	$a24+a23+a22+2^*a21-a12+a13-2^*m$	$a4-2^*a2-a3+2^*m-a1$	a1	a2	$a2+a3-a4$	m-a14	a14
a24	m-a24	$a1-a4+2^*a2+a3-m$	m-a1	m-a2	$a4-a2-a3+m$	m-a15	a15
a23	m-a23	a3	a4	$a1-a4+a2$	$2^*m-a3-a1-a2$	m-a16	a16
a22	m-a22	m-a3	m-a4	$m-a1+a4-a2$	$a3+a1+a2-m$	$a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-2^*m$	$3^*m-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16$
a21	m-a21	$a20+a19+a18+2^*a17-a7+a8-2^*m$	m-a20	m-a19	m-a18	m-a17	$m+a7-a8-a17$
$a13+a21-a12$	$m+a12-a13-a21$	$3^*m-a20-a19-a18-2^*a17+a7-a8$	a20	a19	a18	a17	$a8+a17-a7$

• Details

It is an **algebraic** magic square of order 8 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×6 and embedded with a magic square of order 4. This magic square of order 4 is composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . Since it is composed of all the strips of equal width, we can call it an **algebraic striped** magic square of order 8. Moreover, the external four strips are of equal sums, we can name it as a **algebraic cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 8. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.4. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 8 based on Result 2.4 are given by

8	pan								52	8	mgc								60		
		16	17	18	19	20	-51	-8	21	52			16	17	18	19	20	-45	-6	21	60
		-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	64	-9	22	52			-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	60	-7	22	60
		-118	131	-5	18	12	1	-10	23	52			-112	127	-1	10	11	10	-8	23	60
		33	-20	10	3	13	0	-11	24	52			33	-18	16	5	4	5	-9	24	60
		32	-19	11	2	8	5	-12	25	52			32	-17	12	13	8	-3	-10	25	60
		31	-18	10	3	-7	20	89	-76	52			31	-16	3	2	7	18	85	-70	60
		30	-17	111	-16	-15	-14	-13	-14	52			30	-15	107	-14	-13	-12	-11	-12	60
		31	-18	-98	29	28	27	26	27	52			31	-16	-92	29	28	27	26	27	60
		52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52	52			60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) First Example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 26, S_{8 \times 8} := 52$ and $m := 13$.
- (ii) Second Example: $S_{4 \times 4} := 30, S_{8 \times 8} := 60$ and $m := 15$.

2.3.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.5. An algebraic striped magic square of order 8 in flat way is given by

a5	a6	a7	a8	a9	$4*m-a5-a6-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11$	a10	a11
m-a5	m-a6	m-a7	m-a8	m-a9	$a5+a6+a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-3*m$	m-a10	m-a11
$2*m-a20-a21-a22$	$a20+a21+a22-m$	$a4-2*a2-a3+2*m-a1$	$a1-a4+2*a2+a3-m$	a3	m-a3	m-a12	a12
a22	m-a22	a1	m-a1	a4	m-a4	m-a13	a13
a21	m-a21	a2	m-a2	$a1-a4+a2$	$m-a1+a4-a2$	m-a14	a14
a20	m-a20	$a2+a3-a4$	$a4-a2-a3+m$	$2*m-a3-a1-a2$	$a3+a1+a2-m$	$a12+a13+a14-m$	$2*m-a12-a13-a14$
$a11-a10+a19$	a19	$4*m-a11+a10-2*a19-a18-a17-a16-2*a15-a5+a6$	a18	a17	a16	a15	$a5-a6+a15$
$m-a11+a10-a19$	m-a19	$k5+a19+a18+a17+a16+2*a15+a5-a6-3*m$	m-a18	m-a17	m-a16	m-a15	$m-a5+a6-a15$

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic** magic square of order 8 composed of composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×4 embedded with a magic square of order 4. This magic square of order 4 is composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 . Since it is composed of all the strips of equal width, we can call is an **algebraic striped** magic square of order 8. Moreover, the external four strips are of equal sums, we can name is as a **algebraic cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 8. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$ and $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, where m is the width of the **strip** See below two examples:

Example 2.5. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 8 based on Result 2.5 are given by

8	mgc								64	8	mgc								76		
		14	15	16	17	18	-55	19	20	64			14	15	16	17	18	-43	19	20	76
		2	1	0	-1	-2	71	-3	-4	64			5	4	3	2	1	62	0	-1	76
		-58	74	1	15	12	4	-5	21	64			-52	71	7	12	12	7	-2	21	76
		31	-15	10	6	13	3	-6	22	64			31	-12	10	9	13	6	-3	22	76
		30	-14	11	5	8	8	-7	23	64			30	-11	11	8	8	11	-4	23	76
		29	-13	10	6	-1	17	50	-34	64			29	-10	10	9	5	14	47	-28	76
		29	28	-118	27	26	25	24	23	64			29	28	-106	27	26	25	24	23	76
		-13	-12	134	-11	-10	-9	-8	-7	64			-10	-9	125	-8	-7	-6	-5	-4	76
		64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64			76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76	76

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) **First Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 32, S_{8 \times 8} := 64$ and $m := 16$.
- (ii) **Second Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 38, S_{8 \times 8} := 76$ and $m := 19$.

2.3.3 Cornered

Result 2.6. An **algebraic striped cornered** magic square of order 8 is given by

$a^4 - 2a^2 - a^3 + 2m - a^1$	a^1	a^2	$a^2 + a^3 - a^4$	a^5	$m - a^5$	$m - a^{11}$	a^{11}
$a^1 - a^4 + 2a^2 + a^3 - m$	$m - a^1$	$m - a^2$	$a^4 - a^2 - a^3 + m$	a^6	$m - a^6$	$m - a^{12}$	a^{12}
a^3	a^4	$a^1 - a^4 + a^2$	$2m - a^3 - a^1 - a^2$	a^7	$m - a^7$	$m - a^{13}$	a^{13}
$m - a^3$	$m - a^4$	$m - a^1 + a^4 - a^2$	$a^3 + a^1 + a^2 - m$	$2m - a^5 - a^6 - a^7$	$a^5 + a^6 + a^7 - m$	$m - a^{14}$	a^{14}
$3m - a^5 + a^6 - a^3 - 2a^1 - 2a^2 + a^4 - a^8$	$m - a^8$	$m - a^9$	$a^5 - a^6 + a^3 + 2a^1 + 2a^2 - a^4 + 2a^8 + a^9 + 2a^{10} - 4m$	$m - a^{10}$	$m - a^{10}$	$m - a^{15}$	a^{15}
$a^5 - a^6 + a^3 + 2a^1 + 2a^2 - a^4 + a^8 - 2m$	a^8	a^9	$5m - a^5 + a^6 - a^3 - 2a^1 - 2a^2 + a^4 - 2a^8 - a^9 - 2a^{10}$	a^{10}	a^{10}	$a^{11} + a^{12} + a^{13} + a^{14} + a^{15} - 2m$	$3m - a^{11} - a^{12} - a^{13} - a^{14} - a^{15}$
$a^{11} - a^{12} - 2a^7 - 2a^6 + a^3 + 2a^1 + 2a^2 - a^4 + 2a^8 + 2a^9 + 2a^{10} - a^{16} - 2m$	$m - a^{16}$	$m - a^{17}$	$m - a^{18}$	$m - a^{19}$	$2a^{16} - a^{11} + a^{12} + 2a^{20} + a^{19} - 2a^{10} - 2a^9 - 2a^8 + a^4 - a^3 + a^{18} + 2a^7 + a^{17} + 2a^6 - 2a^2 - 2a^1$	$m - a^{20}$	$m - a^{20}$
$3m - a^{11} + a^{12} + 2a^7 + 2a^6 - a^3 - 2a^1 - 2a^2 + a^4 - 2a^8 - 2a^9 - 2a^{10} + a^{16}$	a^{16}	a^{17}	a^{18}	a^{19}	$m - 2a^{16} + a^{11} - a^{12} - 2a^{20} - a^{19} + 2a^{10} + 2a^9 + 2a^8 - a^4 + a^3 - a^{18} - 2a^7 - a^{17} - 2a^6 + 2a^2 + 2a^1$	a^{20}	a^{20}

• Details

It is an **algebraic cornered striped** magic square of order 8, where the magic squares of orders 4 and 6 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, and $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, where m is the width of the strip. See below two examples:

Example 2.6. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 8 based on Result 2.6 are given by

8	mgc							124	8	mgc							152				
		28	11	12	11	15	16	10	21	124			42	11	12	11	15	23	17	21	152
		3	20	19	20	16	15	9	22	124			-4	27	26	27	16	22	16	22	152
		13	14	9	26	17	14	8	23	124			13	14	9	40	17	21	15	23	152
		18	17	22	5	14	17	7	24	124			25	24	29	-2	28	10	14	24	152
		31	13	12	15	11	11	6	25	124			52	20	19	-13	18	18	13	25	152
		0	18	19	16	20	20	53	-22	124			-14	18	19	51	20	20	39	-1	152
		4	5	4	3	2	104	1	1	124			-10	12	11	10	9	104	8	8	152
		27	26	27	28	29	-73	30	30	124			48	26	27	28	29	-66	30	30	152
		124	124	124	124	124	124	124	124	124			152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 62, S_{6 \times 6} := 93, S_{8 \times 8} := 124$ and $m := 31$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 76, S_{6 \times 6} := 114, S_{8 \times 8} := 152$ and $m := 38$.

2.4 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 10, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.4.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.7. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 10 in cyclic way is given by*

a13	a14	a15	a16	a17	a18	a19	$4*m-a13-a14-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19$	m-a20	a20
m-a13	m-a14	m-a15	m-a16	m-a17	m-a18	m-a19	$a13+a14+a15+a16+a17+a18+a19-3*m$	m-a21	a21
$4*m-a38-a37-a36-a35-a34-2*a33+a20-a21$	$a38+a37+a36+a35+5*a34+2*a33-a20+a21-3*m$	a1	m-a1	a4	m-a4	a7	m-a7	m-a22	a22
a38	m-a38	a2	m-a2	$2*m-a4-a5-a6$	$a4+a5+a6-m$	a8	m-a8	m-a23	a23
a37	m-a37	a3	m-a3	a5	m-a5	$2*m-a7-a8-a9$	$a7+a8+a9-m$	m-a24	a24
a36	m-a36	$2*m-a1-a2-a3$	$a1+a2+a3-m$	a6	m-a6	a9	m-a9	m-a25	a25
a35	m-a35	$m-a7+a8-a5+a6-a10$	m-a10	m-a11	$a7-a8+2*a10+a11+2*a12-a1+a2-2*m$	m-a12	$m+a1-a2+a5-a6-a12$	m-a26	a26
a34	m-a34	$a7-a8+a5-a6+a10$	a10	a11	$3*m-a7+a8-2*a10-a11-2*a12+a1-a2$	a12	$a2-a5+a6+a12-a1$	$a20+a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+a26-3*m$	$4*m-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26$
a33	m-a33	$a32+a31+a30+a29+a28+2*a27-a13+a14-3*m$	m-a32	m-a31	m-a30	m-a29	m-a28	m-a27	$m+a13-a14-a27$
$a21+a33-a20$	$m+a20-a21-a33$	$4*m-a32-a31-a30-a29-a28-2*a27+a13-a14$	a32	a31	a30	a29	a28	a27	$a14+a27-a13$

• Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 10 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. It is again composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$ and $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below few examples:

Example 2.7. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 8 based on Result 2.7 are given by

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/										©IJT	505	10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/										©IJT	580
	38	41	44	47	50	53	56	75	42	59	505		38	41	44	47	50	53	56	135	57	59	580				
	63	60	57	54	51	48	45	26	39	62	505		78	75	72	69	66	63	60	-19	54	62	580				
	-330	431	2	99	11	90	20	81	36	65	505		-270	386	2	114	11	105	20	96	51	65	580				
	113	-12	5	96	160	-59	23	78	33	68	505		113	3	5	111	190	-74	23	93	48	68	580				
	110	-9	8	93	14	87	133	-32	30	71	505		110	6	8	108	14	102	163	-47	45	71	580				
	107	-6	187	-86	17	84	26	75	27	74	505		107	9	217	-101	17	99	26	90	42	74	580				
	104	-3	78	72	69	-42	66	60	24	77	505		104	12	93	87	84	-72	81	75	39	77	580				
	101	0	23	29	32	143	35	41	173	-72	505		101	15	23	29	32	188	35	41	128	-12	580				
	98	3	305	6	9	12	15	18	21	18	505		98	18	260	21	24	27	30	33	36	33	580				
	101	0	-204	95	92	89	86	83	80	83	505		101	15	-144	95	92	89	86	83	80	83	580				
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505		580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580				

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 303, S_{10 \times 10} := 505$ and $m := 101$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 348, S_{10 \times 10} := 580$ and $m := 116$.

Example 2.8. Below are two examples of algebraic striped magic square of order 8 based on Result 2.7 are given by

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/										©IJT	455	10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/										©IJT	590
	40	43	46	49	52	55	58	21	30	61	455		40	43	46	49	52	55	58	129	57	61	590				
	51	48	45	42	39	36	33	70	27	64	455		78	75	72	69	66	63	60	-11	54	64	590				
	-384	475	238	1	4	7	10	13	24	67	455		-276	394	319	1	4	7	10	13	51	67	590				
	115	-24	-147	90	87	84	81	78	21	70	455		115	3	-201	117	114	111	108	105	48	70	590				
	112	-21	16	19	22	256	-65	25	18	73	455		112	6	16	19	22	337	-65	25	45	73	590				
	109	-18	75	72	69	-165	156	66	15	76	455		109	9	102	99	96	-219	183	93	42	76	590				
	106	-15	265	28	-122	31	34	37	12	79	455		106	12	346	28	-122	31	34	37	39	79	590				
	103	-12	-174	63	213	60	57	54	217	-126	455		103	15	-228	90	240	87	84	81	136	-18	590				
	100	-9	349	-6	-3	0	3	6	9	6	455		100	18	268	21	24	27	30	33	36	33	590				
	103	-12	-258	97	94	91	88	85	82	85	455		103	15	-150	97	94	91	88	85	82	85	590				
	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455		590	590	590	590	590	590	590	590	590	590	590				

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 273, S_{10 \times 10} := 455$ and $m := 91$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 354, S_{10 \times 10} := 590$ and $m := 118$.

2.4.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.8. An algebraic striped magic square of order 10 in flat way is given by

a13	a14	a15	a16	a17	a18	a19	$5m - a_{13} - a_{14} - a_{15} - a_{16} - a_{17} - a_{18} - a_{19} - a_{20} - a_{21}$	a20	a21
m-a13	m-a14	m-a15	m-a16	m-a17	m-a18	m-a19	$a_{13} + a_{14} + a_{15} + a_{16} + a_{17} + a_{18} + a_{19} + a_{20} + a_{21} - 4m$	m-a20	m-a21
$3m - a_{38} - a_{37} - a_{36} - a_{35} - a_{34}$	$a_{38} + a_{37} + a_{36} + a_{35} + a_{34} - 2m$	a1	m-a1	a4	m-a4	a7	m-a7	m-a22	a22
a38	m-a38	a2	m-a2	$2m - a_4 - a_5 - a_6$	$a_4 + a_5 + a_6 - m$	a8	m-a8	m-a23	a23
a37	m-a37	a3	m-a3	a5	m-a5	$2m - a_7 - a_8 - a_9$	$a_7 + a_8 + a_9 - m$	m-a24	a24
a36	m-a36	$2m - a_1 - a_2 - a_3$	$a_1 + a_2 + a_3 - m$	a6	m-a6	a9	m-a9	m-a25	a25
a35	m-a35	$m - a_7 + a_8 - a_5 + a_6 - a_{10}$	m-a10	m-a11	$a_7 - a_8 + 2a_{10} + a_{11} + 2a_{12} - a_1 + a_2 - 2m$	m-a12	$m + a_1 - a_2 + a_5 - a_6 - a_{12}$	m-a26	a26
a34	m-a34	$a_7 - a_8 + a_5 - a_6 + a_{10}$	a10	a11	$3m - a_7 + a_8 - 2a_{10} - a_{11} - 2a_{12} + a_1 - a_2$	a12	$a_2 - a_5 + a_6 + a_{12} - a_1$	$a_{22} + a_{23} + a_{24} + a_{25} + a_{26} - 2m$	$3m - a_{22} - a_{23} - a_{24} - a_{25} - a_{26}$
$m + a_{21} - a_{20} - a_{33}$	m-a33	$a_{20} + 2a_{33} + a_{32} + a_{31} + a_{30} + a_{29} + a_{28} + 2a_{27} - a_{13} + a_{14} - 4m - a_{21}$	m-a32	m-a31	m-a30	m-a29	m-a28	m-a27	$m + a_{13} - a_{14} - a_{27}$
$a_{20} + a_{33} - a_{21}$	a33	$5m + a_{21} - a_{20} - 2a_{33} - a_{32} - a_{31} - a_{30} - a_{29} - a_{28} - 2a_{27} + a_{13} - a_{14}$	a32	a31	a30	a29	a28	a27	$a_{14} + a_{27} - a_{13}$

• Details

It is an **algebraic flat-type striped** magic square of order 10 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×10 and two magic rectangles of order 2×6 embedded with a magic square of order 6. It is again composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and one magic rectangle of order 2×6 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$ and $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below few examples:

Example 2.9. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 10 based on Result 2.8 are given by

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										455
		38	41	44	47	50	53	56	5	59	62	455
		53	50	47	44	41	38	35	86	32	29	455
		-262	353	2	89	11	80	20	71	26	65	455
		113	-22	5	86	140	-49	23	68	23	68	455
		110	-19	8	83	14	77	113	-22	20	71	455
		107	-16	167	-76	17	74	26	65	17	74	455
		104	-13	68	62	59	-22	56	50	14	77	455
		101	-10	23	29	32	113	35	41	173	-82	455
		-4	-7	437	-4	-1	2	5	8	11	8	455
		95	98	-346	95	92	89	86	83	80	83	455
		455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										580
		38	41	44	47	50	53	56	130	59	62	580
		78	75	72	69	66	63	60	-14	57	54	580
		-187	303	2	114	11	105	20	96	51	65	580
		113	3	5	111	190	-74	23	93	48	68	580
		110	6	8	108	14	102	163	-47	45	71	580
		107	9	217	-101	17	99	26	90	42	74	580
		104	12	93	87	84	-72	81	75	39	77	580
		101	15	23	29	32	188	35	41	123	-7	580
		21	18	337	21	24	27	30	33	36	33	580
		95	98	-221	95	92	89	86	83	80	83	580
		580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 273, S_{10 \times 10} := 455$ and $m := 91$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 348, S_{10 \times 10} := 580$ and $m := 116$.

Example 2.10. Below are two examples of *algebraic striped* magic square of order 10 based on Result 2.8 are given by

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										455
		38	41	44	47	50	53	56	5	59	62	455
		53	50	47	44	41	38	35	86	32	29	455
		-262	353	2	5	8	167	20	71	26	65	455
		113	-22	89	86	83	-76	23	68	23	68	455
		110	-19	11	140	14	17	113	-22	20	71	455
		107	-16	80	-49	77	74	26	65	17	74	455
		104	-13	68	62	59	-22	56	50	14	77	455
		101	-10	23	29	32	113	35	41	173	-82	455
		-4	-7	437	-4	-1	2	5	8	11	8	455
		95	98	-346	95	92	89	86	83	80	83	455
		455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455	455

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										580
		38	41	44	47	50	53	56	130	59	62	580
		78	75	72	69	66	63	60	-14	57	54	580
		-187	303	2	5	8	217	20	96	51	65	580
		113	3	114	111	108	-101	23	93	48	68	580
		110	6	11	190	14	17	163	-47	45	71	580
		107	9	105	-74	102	99	26	90	42	74	580
		104	12	93	87	84	-72	81	75	39	77	580
		101	15	23	29	32	188	35	41	123	-7	580
		21	18	337	21	24	27	30	33	36	33	580
		95	98	-221	95	92	89	86	83	80	83	580
		580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580	580

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 273, S_{10 \times 10} := 455$ and $m := 91$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 348, S_{10 \times 10} := 580$ and $m := 116$.

Result 2.9. An *algebraic striped* magic square of order 10 in *flat way* is given by

a14	a15	a16	a17	a18	a19	a20	$5*m-a14-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22$	a21	a22
m-a14	m-a15	m-a16	m-a17	m-a18	m-a19	m-a20	$a14+a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22-4*m$	m-a21	m-a22
$3*m-a39-a38-a37-a36-a35$	$a39+a38+a37+a36+a35-2*m$	$3*m-a2-a3-a1-a5-a4$	$a1+a5+a4+a2+a3-2*m$	a6	m-a6	$3*m-2*a1-2*a4+a10+a12-a13-a2-a3$	$2*a1+2*a4-a10-a12+a13+a2+a3-2*m$	m-a23	a23
a39	m-a39	a1	m-a1	a7	m-a7	a10	m-a10	m-a24	a24
a38	m-a38	a2	m-a2	a8	m-a8	$2*a1+2*a4-2*a10-2*a12+a2+a3-a11$	$m-2*a1-2*a4+2*a10+2*a12-a2-a3+a11$	m-a25	a25
a37	m-a37	a3	m-a3	$a8+3*m-2*a1+a12-a13-a2-a3-a5-a4$	$a5+a4-a8+2*a1-a12+a13+a2+a3-2*m$	a11	m-a11	m-a26	a26
a36	m-a36	a4	m-a4	$a5+a4+2*a1-a12+a13+a2+a3-a9-a6-a7-2*a8$	$m+a6+a7+2*a8-a5-a4-2*a1+a12-a13-a2-a3+a9$	a12	m-a12	m-a27	a27
a35	m-a35	a5	m-a5	a9	m-a9	a13	m-a13	$a23+a24+a25+a26+a27-2*m$	$3*m-a23-a24-a25-a26-a27$
$m+a22-a21-a34$	m-a34	$a21+2*a34+a33+a32+a31+a30+a29+2*a28-a14+a15-4*m-a22$	m-a33	m-a32	m-a31	m-a30	m-a29	m-a28	$m+a14-a15-a28$
$a21+a34-a22$	a34	$5*m+a22-a21-2*a34-a33-a32-a31-a30-a29-2*a28+a14-a15$	a33	a32	a31	a30	a29	a28	$a15+a28-a14$

Example 2.11. Below are two examples of *algebraic striped magic square* of order 10 based on Result 2.9 are given by

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										410
		41	44	47	50	53	56	59	-67	62	65	410
		41	38	35	32	29	26	23	149	20	17	410
		-304	386	206	-124	17	65	233	-151	14	68	410
		116	-34	2	80	20	62	29	53	11	71	410
		113	-31	5	77	23	59	-121	203	8	74	410
		110	-28	8	74	224	-142	32	50	5	77	410
		107	-25	11	71	-64	146	35	47	2	80	410
		104	-22	14	68	26	56	38	44	206	-124	410
		-16	-19	500	-16	-13	-10	-7	-4	-1	-4	410
		98	101	-418	98	95	92	89	86	83	86	410
		410	410	410	410	410	410	410	410	410	410	410

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										595
		41	44	47	50	53	56	59	118	62	65	595
		78	75	72	69	66	63	60	1	57	54	595
		-193	312	317	-198	17	102	344	-225	51	68	595
		116	3	2	117	20	99	29	90	48	71	595
		113	6	5	114	23	96	-121	240	45	74	595
		110	9	8	111	335	-216	32	87	42	77	595
		107	12	11	108	-64	183	35	84	39	80	595
		104	15	14	105	26	93	38	81	132	-13	595
		21	18	352	21	24	27	30	33	36	33	595
		98	101	-233	98	95	92	89	86	83	86	595
		595	595	595	595	595	595	595	595	595	595	595

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 246, S_{10 \times 10} := 410$ and $m := 82$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 357, S_{10 \times 10} := 595$ and $m := 119$.

2.4.3 Cornered

Result 2.10. *An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 10 is given by*

$a_4 - 2a_2 - a_3 + 2m - a_1$	a_1	a_2	$a_2 + a_3 - a_4$	a_5	$m - a_5$	$m - a_{11}$	a_{11}	$m - a_{21}$	a_{21}
$a_1 - a_4 + 2a_2 + a_3 - m$	$m - a_1$	$m - a_2$	$a_4 - a_2 - a_3 + m$	a_6	$m - a_6$	$m - a_{12}$	a_{12}	$m - a_{22}$	a_{22}
a_3	a_4	$a_1 - a_4 + a_2$	$2m - a_3 - a_1 - a_2$	a_7	$m - a_7$	$m - a_{13}$	a_{13}	$m - a_{23}$	a_{23}
$m - a_3$	$m - a_4$	$m - a_1 + a_4 - a_2$	$a_3 + a_1 + a_2 - m$	$2m - a_5 - a_6 - a_7$	$a_5 + a_6 + a_7 - m$	$m - a_{14}$	a_{14}	$m - a_{24}$	a_{24}
$3m - a_5 + a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - a_8$	$m - a_8$	$m - a_9$	$a_5 - a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + 2a_8 + a_9 + 2a_{10} - 4m$	$m - a_{10}$	$m - a_{10}$	$m - a_{15}$	a_{15}	$m - a_{25}$	a_{25}
$a_5 - a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + a_8 - 2m$	a_8	a_9	$5m - a_5 + a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - 2a_8 - a_9 - 2a_{10}$	a_{10}	a_{10}	$a_{11} + a_{12} + a_{13} + a_{14} + a_{15} - 2m$	$3m - a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{13} - a_{14} - a_{15}$	$m - a_{26}$	a_{26}
$a_{11} - a_{12} - 2a_7 - 2a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + 2a_8 + 2a_9 + 2a_{10} - a_{16} - 2m$	$m - a_{16}$	$m - a_{17}$	$m - a_{18}$	$m - a_{19}$	$2a_{16} - a_{11} + a_{12} + 2a_{20} + a_{19} - 2a_{10} - 2a_9 - 2a_8 + a_4 - a_3 + a_{18} + 2a_7 + a_{17} + 2a_6 - 2a_2 - 2a_1$	$m - a_{20}$	$m - a_{20}$	$m - a_{27}$	a_{27}
$3m - a_{11} + a_{12} + 2a_7 + 2a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - 2a_8 - 2a_9 - 2a_{10} + a_{16}$	a_{16}	a_{17}	a_{18}	a_{19}	$m - 2a_{16} + a_{11} - a_{12} - 2a_{20} - a_{19} + 2a_{10} + 2a_9 + 2a_8 - a_4 + a_3 - a_{18} - 2a_7 - a_{17} - 2a_6 + 2a_2 + 2a_1$	a_{20}	a_{20}	$a_{21} + a_{22} + a_{23} + a_{24} + a_{25} + a_{26} + a_{27} - 3m$	$4m - a_{21} - a_{22} - a_{23} - a_{24} - a_{25} - a_{26} - a_{27}$
$m + a_{21} - a_{22} + a_{13} - a_{14} - a_{18} + a_{17} - a_{28}$	$m - a_{28}$	$m - a_{29}$	$m - a_{30}$	$m - a_{31}$	$m - a_{32}$	$m - a_{33}$	$a_{18} - a_{17} - a_{13} + a_{14} + 2a_{34} + a_3 + a_{32} + a_{31} + a_{30} + a_{29} + 2a_{28} + a_{22} - a_{21} - 4m$	$m - a_{34}$	$m - a_{34}$
$a_{22} - a_{13} + a_{14} + a_{18} - a_{17} + a_{28} - a_{21}$	a_{28}	a_{29}	a_{30}	a_{31}	a_{32}	a_{33}	$5m - a_{18} + a_{17} + a_{13} - a_{14} - 2a_{34} - a_{33} - a_{32} - a_{31} - a_{30} - a_{29} - 2a_{28} - a_{22} + a_{21}$	a_{34}	a_{34}

• Details

It is an *algebraic cornered striped* magic square of order 10, where the magic squares of order 4, 6 and 8 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$ and $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, where m is the width of the *strip*. See below two examples:

Example 2.12. Below are two examples of *algebraic striped* magic square of order 10 based on Result 2.10 are given by

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180									
65	2	3	2	6	30	24	12	14	22	180	75	2	3	2	6	35	29	12	19	22	205
-29	34	33	34	7	29	23	13	13	23	180	-34	39	38	39	7	34	28	13	18	23	205
4	5	0	63	8	28	22	14	12	24	180	4	5	0	73	8	33	27	14	17	24	205
32	31	36	-27	51	-15	21	15	11	25	180	37	36	41	-32	61	-20	26	15	16	25	205
91	27	26	-86	25	25	20	16	10	26	180	106	32	31	-106	30	30	25	16	15	26	205
-55	9	10	122	11	11	-2	38	9	27	180	-65	9	10	147	11	11	-12	53	14	27	205
-51	19	18	17	16	95	15	15	8	28	180	-61	24	23	22	21	95	20	20	13	28	205
87	17	18	19	20	-59	21	21	67	-31	180	102	17	18	19	20	-54	21	21	52	-11	205
4	7	6	5	4	3	2	147	1	1	180	9	12	11	10	9	8	7	127	6	6	205
32	29	30	31	32	33	34	-111	35	35	180	32	29	30	31	32	33	34	-86	35	35	205
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205	205

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 72, S_{6 \times 6} := 108, S_{8 \times 8} := 144, S_{10 \times 10} := 180$ and $m := 36$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 82, S_{6 \times 6} := 103, S_{8 \times 8} := 164, S_{10 \times 10} := 205$ and $m := 41$.

Remark 2.1. We have given above three different ways of writing *algebraic striped* magic square of order 10. The more examples are given because of different combinations of *algebraic striped* magic squares of order 6. The following subsection brings only three types of results and examples.

2.5 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 12, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.5.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.11. An *algebraic striped* magic square of order 12 in *cyclic way* is given by

a25	a26	a27	a28	a29	a30	a31	a32	a33	$5m-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33$	m-a34	a34
m-a25	m-a26	m-a27	m-a28	m-a29	m-a30	m-a31	m-a32	m-a33	$a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33-4m$	m-a35	a35
$5m-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-2a51+a34-a35$	$a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+2a51-a34+a35-4m$	a7	a8	a9	a10	a11	$3m-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11$	m-a12	a12	m-a36	a36
a58	m-a58	m-a7	m-a8	m-a9	m-a10	m-a11	$a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-2m$	m-a13	a13	m-a37	a37
a57	m-a57	$3m-a24-a23-a22-2a21+a12-a13$	$a24+a23+a22+2a21-a12+a13-2m$	$a4-2a2-a3+2m-a1$	a1	a2	$a2+a3-a4$	m-a14	a14	m-a38	a38
a56	m-a56	a24	m-a24	$a1-a4+2a2+a3-m$	m-a1	m-a2	$a4-a2-a3+m$	m-a15	a15	m-a39	a39
a55	m-a55	a23	m-a23	a3	a4	$a1-a4+a2$	$2m-a3-a1-a2$	m-a16	a16	m-a40	a40
a54	m-a54	a22	m-a22	m-a3	m-a4	$m-a1+a4-a2$	$a3+a1+a2-m$	$a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-2m$	$3m-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16$	m-a41	a41
a53	m-a53	a21	m-a21	$a20+a19+a18+2a17-a7+a8-2m$	m-a20	m-a19	m-a18	m-a17	$m+a7-a8-a17$	m-a42	a42
a52	m-a52	$a13+a21-a12$	$m+a12-a13-a21$	$3m-a20-a19-a18-2a17+a7-a8$	a20	a19	a18	a17	$a8+a17-a7$	$a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a41+a42-4m$	$5m-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a41-a42$
a51	m-a51	$a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+2a43-a25+a26-4m$	m-a50	m-a49	m-a48	m-a47	m-a46	m-a45	m-a44	m-a43	$m+a25-a26-a43$
$a35+a51-a34$	$m+a34-a35-a51$	$5m-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-2a43+a25-a26$	a50	a49	a48	a47	a46	a45	a44	a43	$a26+a43-a25$

• Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic-type striped** magic square of order 12 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×10 embedded with a magic square of order 8 with four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 having magic square of order 4 in the middle. It is again divided in two equal sum magic rectangles of order 2×4 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$ where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.13. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 12 based on Result 2.11 are given by

12	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	612	12	mgc	12x12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	714															
	74	77	80	83	86	89	92	95	98	-264	1	101	612		74	77	80	83	86	89	92	95	98	-179	18	101	714	
	28	25	22	19	16	13	10	7	4	366	-2	104	612		45	42	39	36	33	30	27	24	21	298	15	104	714	
	-945	1047	20	23	26	29	32	176	67	35	-5	107	612		-860	979	20	23	26	29	32	227	84	35	12	107	714	
	173	-71	82	79	76	73	70	-74	64	38	-8	110	612		173	-54	99	96	93	90	87	-108	81	38	9	110	714	
	170	-68	-25	127	195	2	5	2	61	41	-11	113	612		170	-51	26	93	229	2	5	2	78	41	6	113	714	
	167	-65	71	31	-93	100	97	100	58	44	-14	116	612		167	-48	71	48	-110	117	114	117	75	44	3	116	714	
	164	-62	68	34	8	11	-4	189	55	47	-17	119	612		164	-45	68	51	8	11	-4	223	72	47	0	119	714	
	161	-59	65	37	94	91	106	-87	1	101	-20	122	612		161	-42	65	54	111	108	123	-104	-33	152	-3	122	714	
	158	-56	62	40	67	43	46	49	52	49	-23	125	612		158	-39	62	57	33	60	63	66	69	66	-6	125	714	
	155	-53	65	37	35	59	56	53	50	53	609	-507	612		155	-36	65	54	86	59	56	53	50	53	541	-422	714	
	152	-50	831	-47	-44	-41	-38	-35	-32	-29	-26	-29	612		152	-33	763	-30	-27	-24	-21	-18	-15	-12	-9	-12	714	
	155	-53	-729	149	146	143	140	137	134	131	128	131	612		155	-36	-644	149	146	143	140	137	134	131	128	131	714	
	612	612	612	612	612	612	612	612	612	612	612	612	612		714	714	714	714	714	714	714	714	714	714	714	714	714	714

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 204, S_{8 \times 8} := 408, S_{12 \times 12} := 612$ and $m := 102$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 238, S_{8 \times 8} := 476, S_{12 \times 12} := 714$ and $m := 119$.

2.5.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.12. An algebraic striped magic square of order 12 in flat way is given by

a23	a24	a25	a26	a27	a28	a29	a30	a31	$6*m-a23-a24-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33$	a32	a33
m-a23	m-a24	m-a25	m-a26	m-a27	m-a28	m-a29	m-a30	m-a31	$a23+a24+a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33-5*m$	m-a32	m-a33
$4*m-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-a51-a50$	$a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+a51+a50-3*m$	a5	a6	a7	a8	a9	$4*m-a5-a6-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11$	a10	a11	m-a34	a34
a56	m-a56	m-a5	m-a6	m-a7	m-a8	m-a9	$a5+a6+a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-3*m$	m-a10	m-a11	m-a35	a35
a55	m-a55	$2*m-a20-a21-a22$	$a20+a21+a22-m$	$a4-2*a2-a3+2*m-a1$	$a1-a4+2*a2+a3-m$	a3	m-a3	m-a12	a12	m-a36	a36
a54	m-a54	a22	m-a22	a1	m-a1	a4	m-a4	m-a13	a13	m-a37	a37
a53	m-a53	a21	m-a21	a2	m-a2	$a1-a4+a2$	$m-a1+a4-a2$	m-a14	a14	m-a38	a38
a52	m-a52	a20	m-a20	$a2+a3-a4$	$a4-a2-a3+m$	$2*m-a3-a1-a2$	$a3+a1+a2-m$	$a12+a13+a14-m$	$2*m-a12-a13-a14$	m-a39	a39
a51	m-a51	$a11-a10+a19$	a19	$4*m-a11+a10-2*a19-a18-a17-a16-2*a15-a5+a6$	a18	a17	a16	a15	$a5-a6+a15$	m-a40	a40
a50	m-a50	$m-a11+a10-a19$	m-a19	$a19+a11-a10+a19+a18+a17+a16+2*a15+a5-a6-3*m$	m-a18	m-a17	m-a16	m-a15	$m-a5+a6-a15$	$a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40-3*m$	$4*m-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40$
$m+a33-a32-a49$	m-a49	$a32+2*a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+2*a41-a23+a24-5*m-a33$	m-a48	m-a47	m-a46	m-a45	m-a44	m-a43	m-a42	m-a41	$m+a23-a24-a41$
$a32+a49-a33$	a49	$6*m+a33-a32-2*a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-2*a41+a23-a24$	a48	a47	a46	a45	a44	a43	a42	a41	$a24+a41-a23$

• Details

It is an *algebraic flat-type striped* magic square of order 12 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×12 and two magic rectangles of order 2×8 embedded with a magic square of order 8. It is again composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and two magic rectangles of order 2×4 embedded with a magic square of order 4. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$ where m is the width of the *strip*. See below two examples:

Example 2.14. Below are two examples of *algebraic striped* magic square of order 12 based on Result 2.12 are given by

12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											348
	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	29	33	34	348
	34	33	32	31	30	29	28	27	26	29	25	24	348
	-146	204	6	7	8	9	10	169	11	12	23	35	348
	57	1	52	51	50	49	48	-111	47	46	22	36	348
	56	2	50	8	109	-51	4	54	45	13	21	37	348
	55	3	23	35	2	56	5	53	44	14	20	38	348
	54	4	22	36	3	55	0	58	43	15	19	39	348
	53	5	21	37	2	56	107	-49	-16	74	18	40	348
	52	6	21	20	106	19	18	17	16	15	17	41	348
	51	7	37	38	-48	39	40	41	42	43	92	-34	348
	9	8	216	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	15	348
	49	50	-158	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	43	348
	348	348	348	348	348	348	348	348	348	348	348	348	348

12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											366
	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	47	33	34	366
	37	36	35	34	33	32	31	30	29	14	28	27	366
	-134	195	6	7	8	9	10	181	11	12	26	35	366
	57	4	55	54	53	52	51	-120	50	49	25	36	366
	56	5	56	5	115	-54	4	57	48	13	24	37	366
	55	6	23	38	2	59	5	56	47	14	23	38	366
	54	7	22	39	3	58	0	61	46	15	22	39	366
	53	8	21	40	2	59	113	-52	-19	80	21	40	366
	52	9	21	20	118	19	18	17	16	15	20	41	366
	51	10	40	41	-57	42	43	44	45	46	83	-22	366
	12	11	201	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	18	366
	49	50	-140	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	43	366
	366	366	366	366	366	366	366	366	366	366	366	366	366

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 116, S_{8 \times 8} := 232, S_{12 \times 12} := 348$ and $m := 58$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 122, S_{8 \times 8} := 244, S_{12 \times 12} := 366$ and $m := 61$.

2.5.3 Cornered

Result 2.13. *An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 12 is given by*

$a_4 - 2a_2 - a_3 + 2m - a_1$	a_1	a_2	$a_2 + a_3 - a_4$	a_5	$m - a_5$	$m - a_{11}$	a_{11}	$m - a_{21}$	a_{21}	$m - a_{35}$	a_{35}
$a_1 - a_4 + 2a_2 + a_3 - m$	$m - a_1$	$m - a_2$	$a_4 - a_2 - a_3 + m$	a_6	$m - a_6$	$m - a_{12}$	a_{12}	$m - a_{22}$	a_{22}	$m - a_{36}$	a_{36}
a_3	a_4	$a_1 - a_4 + a_2$	$2m - a_3 - a_1 - a_2$	a_7	$m - a_7$	$m - a_{13}$	a_{13}	$m - a_{23}$	a_{23}	$m - a_{37}$	a_{37}
$m - a_3$	$m - a_4$	$m - a_1 + a_4 - a_2$	$a_3 + a_1 + a_2 - m$	$2m - a_5 - a_6 - a_7$	$a_5 + a_6 + a_7 - m$	$m - a_{14}$	a_{14}	$m - a_{24}$	a_{24}	$m - a_{38}$	a_{38}
$3m - a_5 + a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - a_8$	$m - a_8$	$m - a_9$	$a_5 - a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + 2a_8 + a_9 + 2a_{10} - 4m$	$m - a_{10}$	$m - a_{10}$	$m - a_{15}$	a_{15}	$m - a_{25}$	a_{25}	$m - a_{39}$	a_{39}
$a_5 - a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + a_8 - 2m$	a_8	a_9	$5m - a_5 + a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - 2a_8 - a_9 - 2a_{10}$	a_{10}	a_{10}	$a_{11} + a_{12} + a_{13} + a_{14} + a_{15} - 5 \cdot 2m$	$3m - a_{11} - a_{12} - a_{13} - a_{14} - a_{15}$	$m - a_{26}$	a_{26}	$m - a_{40}$	a_{40}
$a_{11} - a_{12} - 2a_7 - 2a_6 + a_3 + 2a_1 + 2a_2 - a_4 + 2a_8 + 2a_9 + 2a_{10} - a_{16} - 2m$	$m - a_{16}$	$m - a_{17}$	$m - a_{18}$	$m - a_{19}$	$2a_{16} - a_{11} + a_{12} + 2a_{20} + a_{19} - 2a_{10} - 2a_9 - 2a_8 + a_4 - a_3 + a_{18} + 2a_7 + a_{17} + 2a_6 - 2a_2 - 2a_1$	$m - a_{20}$	$m - a_{20}$	$m - a_{27}$	a_{27}	$m - a_{41}$	a_{41}
$3m - a_{11} + a_{12} + 2a_7 + 2a_6 - a_3 - 2a_1 - 2a_2 + a_4 - 2a_8 - 2a_9 - 2a_{10} + a_{16}$	a_{16}	a_{17}	a_{18}	a_{19}	$m - 2a_{16} + a_{11} - a_{12} - 2a_{20} - a_{19} + 2a_{10} + 2a_9 + 2a_8 - a_4 + a_3 - a_{18} - 2a_7 - a_{17} - 2a_6 + 2a_2 + 2a_1$	a_{20}	a_{20}	$a_{21} + a_{22} + a_{23} + a_{24} + a_{25} + a_{26} + a_{27} - 7 \cdot 3m$	$4m - a_{21} - a_{22} - a_{23} - a_{24} - a_{25} - a_{26} - a_{27}$	$m - a_{42}$	a_{42}
$m + a_{21} - a_{22} + a_{13} - a_{14} - a_{18} + a_{17} - a_{28}$	$m - a_{28}$	$m - a_{29}$	$m - a_{30}$	$m - a_{31}$	$m - a_{32}$	$m - a_{33}$	$a_{18} - a_{17} - a_{13} + a_{14} + 2a_{34} + a_{33} + a_{32} + a_{31} + a_{30} + a_{29} + 2a_{28} + a_{22} - a_{21} - 4m$	$m - a_{34}$	$m - a_{34}$	$m - a_{43}$	a_{43}
$a_{22} - a_{13} + a_{14} + a_{18} - a_{17} + a_{28} - a_{21}$	a_{28}	a_{29}	a_{30}	a_{31}	a_{32}	a_{33}	$5m - a_{18} + a_{17} + a_{13} - a_{14} - 2a_{34} - a_{33} - a_{32} - a_{31} - a_{30} - a_{29} - 2a_{28} - a_{22} + a_{21}$	a_{34}	a_{34}	$a_{35} + a_{36} + a_{37} + a_{38} + a_{39} + a_{40} + a_{41} + a_{42} + a_{43} - 4m$	$5m - a_{35} - a_{36} - a_{37} - a_{38} - a_{39} - a_{40} - a_{41} - a_{42} - a_{43}$
$2a_7 + 2a_6 - 2a_8 - 2a_{10} - 2a_9 + 2a_{20} + 2a_{19} + 2a_{16} + 2a_{12} + 2a_{15} + a_{35} + a_{18} + a_{17} + a_{13} + a_{14} - a_3 + a_4 - a_{30} + a_{29} - a_{36} + a_{23} - a_{24} - 3m - a_{44} - 2a_2 - 2a_1$	$m - a_{44}$	$m - a_{45}$	$m - a_{46}$	$m - a_{47}$	$m - a_{48}$	$m - a_{49}$	$m - a_{50}$	$m - a_{51}$	$2a_{44} + 2a_2 + 2a_1 - 2a_7 - 2a_6 + 2a_8 + 2a_{10} + 2a_9 - 2a_{20} - 2a_{19} - 2a_{16} - 2a_{12} - 2a_{15} - a_{35} - a_{18} - a_{17} - a_{13} - a_{14} + a_3 - a_4 + a_{30} - a_{29} + a_{36} + a_{50} + a_{51} + 2a_{52} + a_4 + 5a_{46} + a_{47} + a_{48} + a_{49} - a_{23} + a_{24} - m$	$m - a_{52}$	$m - a_{52}$
$a_{44} + 2a_2 + 2a_1 - 2a_7 - 2a_6 + 2a_8 + 2a_{10} + 2a_9 - 2a_{20} - 2a_{19} - 2a_{16} - 2a_{12} - 2a_{15} - a_{35} - a_{18} - a_{17} - a_{13} - a_{14} + a_3 - a_4 + a_{30} - a_{29} + a_{36} - a_{23} + a_{24} + 4m$	a_{44}	a_{45}	a_{46}	a_{47}	a_{48}	a_{49}	a_{50}	a_{51}	$2a_7 + 2a_6 - 2a_8 - 2a_{10} - 2a_9 + 2a_{20} + 2a_{19} + 2a_{16} + 2a_{12} + 2a_{15} + a_{35} + a_{18} + a_{17} + a_{13} + a_{14} - a_3 + a_4 - a_{30} + a_{29} - a_{36} - a_{50} - a_{51} - 2a_{52} - a_{45} - a_{46} - a_{47} - a_{48} - a_{49} + a_{23} - a_{24} + 2m - 2a_{44} - 2a_2 - 2a_1$	a_{52}	a_{52}

• Details

It is an **algebraic cornered striped** magic square of order 12, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8 and 10 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, where m is the width of the strip. See below two examples:

Example 2.15. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 12 based on Result 2.13 are given by

12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												318
102	1	2	1	5	48	42	11	32	21	18	35	318		
-49	52	51	52	6	47	41	12	31	22	17	36	318		
3	4	-1	100	7	46	40	13	30	23	16	37	318		
50	49	54	-47	88	-35	39	14	29	24	15	38	318		
147	45	44	-163	43	43	38	15	28	25	14	39	318		
-94	8	9	216	10	10	-41	94	27	26	13	40	318		
-90	37	36	35	34	94	33	33	26	27	12	41	318		
143	16	17	18	19	-41	20	20	9	44	11	42	318		
22	25	24	23	22	21	20	70	19	19	10	43	318		
31	28	29	30	31	32	33	-17	34	34	139	-86	318		
-13	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	285	1	1	318		
66	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-232	52	52	318		
318	318	318	318	318	318	318	318	318	318	318	318	318		

12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT												372
120	1	2	1	5	57	51	11	41	21	27	35	372		
-58	61	60	61	6	56	50	12	40	22	26	36	372		
3	4	-1	118	7	55	49	13	39	23	25	37	372		
59	58	63	-56	106	-44	48	14	38	24	24	38	372		
174	54	53	-199	52	52	47	15	37	25	23	39	372		
-112	8	9	261	10	10	-59	121	36	26	22	40	372		
-108	46	45	44	43	94	42	42	35	27	21	41	372		
170	16	17	18	19	-32	20	20	-18	80	20	42	372		
31	34	33	32	31	30	29	34	28	28	19	43	372		
31	28	29	30	31	32	33	28	34	34	103	-41	372		
-40	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	276	10	10	372		
102	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-214	52	52	372		
372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372	372		

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 106, S_{6 \times 6} := 159, S_{8 \times 8} := 212, S_{10 \times 10} := 265, S_{12 \times 12} := 318$ and $m := 53$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 124, S_{6 \times 6} := 186, S_{8 \times 8} := 244, S_{10 \times 10} := 310, S_{12 \times 12} := 372$ and $m := 62$.

2.6 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 14

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 14, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.6.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.14. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 14 in cyclic way is given by*

a40	a41	a42	a43	a44	a45	a46	a47	a48	a49	a50	$6m-a44-a43-a42-a40-a41-a50-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49$	m-a51	a51
m-a40	m-a41	m-a42	m-a43	m-a44	m-a45	m-a46	m-a47	m-a48	m-a49	m-a50	$a44+a43+a42+a40+a41+a50+a45+a46+a47+a48+a49-5m$	m-a52	a52
$6m-a73-a75-a74-a77-a76-a78-a80-a79-a81-2a72+a51-a52$	$a73+a75+a74+a77+a76+a78+a80+a79+a81+2a72-a51+a52-5m$	a14	a15	a16	a17	a18	a19	a20	$4m-a14-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20$	m-a21	a21	m-a53	a53
a81	m-a81	m-a14	m-a15	m-a16	m-a17	m-a18	m-a19	m-a20	$a14+a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20-3m$	m-a22	a22	m-a54	a54
a80	m-a80	$4m-a39-a38-a37-a36-a35-2a34+a21-a22$	$a39+a38+a37+a36+a35+2a34-a21+a22-3m$	$3m-a2-a3-a1-a5-a4$	a1	a2	a3	a4	a5	m-a23	a23	m-a55	a55
a79	m-a79	a39	m-a39	$a1+a5+a4+a2+a3-2m$	m-a1	m-a2	m-a3	m-a4	m-a5	m-a24	a24	m-a56	a56
a78	m-a78	a38	m-a38	a6	a7	a8	$a8+3m-2a1+a12-a13-a2-a3-a5-a4$	$a5+a4+2a1-a12+a13+a2+a3-a9-a6-a7-2a8$	a9	m-a25	a25	m-a57	a57
a77	m-a77	a37	m-a37	m-a6	m-a7	m-a8	$a5+a4-a8+2a1-a12+a13+a2+a3-2m$	$m+a6+a7+2a8-a5-a4-2a1+a12-a13-a2-a3+a9$	m-a9	m-a26	a26	m-a58	a58
a76	m-a76	a36	m-a36	$3m-2a1-2a4+a10+a12-a13-a2-a3$	a10	$(2a1+2a4-2a10-2a12+a2+a3-a11)$	a11	a12	a13	m-a27	a27	m-a59	a59
a75	m-a75	a35	m-a35	$2a1+2a4-a10-a12+a13+a2+a3-2m$	m-a10	$m-2a1-2a4+2a10+2a12-a2-a3+a11$	m-a11	m-a12	m-a13	$a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+a26+a27-3m$	$4m-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26-a27$	m-a60	a60
a74	m-a74	a34	m-a34	$a33+a32+a31+a30+a29+2a28-a14+a15-3m$	m-a33	m-a32	m-a31	m-a30	m-a29	m-a28	$m+a14-a15-a28$	m-a61	a61
a73	m-a73	$a22+a34-a21$	$m+a21-a22-a34$	$4m-a33-a32-a31-a30-a29-2a28+a14-a15$	a33	a32	a31	a30	a29	a28	$a15+a28-a14$	$a61+a60+a58+a59+a57+a55+a56+a54+a53+a51+a52-5m$	$6m-a61-a60-a58-a59-a57-a55-a56-a54-a53-a51-a52$
a72	m-a72	$a67+a68+2a62+a66+a65+a64-a40+a41+a71+a70+a69+a63-5m$	m-a71	m-a70	m-a69	m-a68	m-a67	m-a66	m-a65	m-a64	m-a63	m-a62	$m+a40-a41-a62$
$a52+a72-a51$	$m+a51-a52-a72$	$6m-a67-a68-2a62-a66-a65-a64+a40-a41-a71-a70-a69-a63$	a71	a70	a69	a68	a67	a66	a65	a64	a63	a62	$a41+a62-a40$

• Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic striped** magic square of order 14 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×12 embedded with a magic square of order 10. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. It is again composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×6 . In this case the magic sums are , $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.16. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 14 based on Result 2.14 are given by

14	mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	497								
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-69	20	51	497
31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	140	19	52	497
-412	483	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	165	50	21	18	53	497
81	-10	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	-94	49	22	17	54	497
80	-9	30	41	198	1	2	3	4	5	48	23	16	55	497
79	-8	39	32	-127	70	69	68	67	66	47	24	15	56	497
78	-7	38	33	6	7	8	204	-21	9	46	25	14	57	497
77	-6	37	34	65	64	63	-133	92	62	45	26	13	58	497
76	-5	36	35	207	10	-40	11	12	13	44	27	12	59	497
75	-4	35	36	-136	61	111	60	59	58	-45	116	11	60	497
74	-3	34	37	-1	38	39	40	41	42	43	42	10	61	497
73	-2	35	36	72	33	32	31	30	29	28	29	261	-190	497
72	-1	373	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	8	497
73	-2	-302	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	497
497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497	497

14	mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	574								
40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-3	31	51	574
42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	85	30	52	574
-346	428	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	209	61	21	29	53	574
81	1	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	-127	60	22	28	54	574
80	2	74	8	231	1	2	3	4	5	59	23	27	55	574
79	3	39	43	-149	81	80	79	78	77	58	24	26	56	574
78	4	38	44	6	7	8	237	-21	9	57	25	25	57	574
77	5	37	45	76	75	74	-155	103	73	56	26	24	58	574
76	6	36	46	240	10	-40	11	12	13	55	27	23	59	574
75	7	35	47	-158	72	122	71	70	69	-78	160	22	60	574
74	8	34	48	-34	49	50	51	52	53	54	53	21	61	574
73	9	35	47	116	33	32	31	30	29	28	29	206	-124	574
72	10	318	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	19	574
73	9	-236	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	574
574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574	574

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 213, S_{10 \times 10} := 355, S_{14 \times 14} := 497$ and $m := 71$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 246, S_{10 \times 10} := 410, S_{14 \times 14} := 574$ and $m := 82$.

2.6.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.15. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 14 in flat way is given by*

a39	a40	a41	a42	a43	a44	a45	a46	a47	a48	a49	$7*a81-a51-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-a41-a40-a39$	a50	a51
a81-a39	a81-a40	a81-a41	a81-a42	a81-a43	a81-a44	a81-a45	a81-a46	a81-a47	a81-a48	a81-a49	$a51+a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+a41+a40+a39-6*a81$	a81-a50	a81-a51
$5*a81-a80-a79-a78-a77-a76-a75-a74-a73-a72$	$a80+a79+a78+a77+a76+a75+a74+a73+a72-4*a81$	a13	a14	a15	a16	a17	a18	a19	$5*a81-a13-a14-a15-a16-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21$	a20	a21	a81-a52	a52
a80	a81-a80	a81-a13	a81-a14	a81-a15	a81-a16	a81-a17	a81-a18	a81-a19	$a13+a14+a15+a16+a17+a18+a19+a20+a21-4*a81$	a81-a20	a81-a21	a81-a53	a53
a79	a81-a79	$3*a81-a38-a37-a36-a35-a34$	$a38+a37+a36+a35+a34-2*a81$	a1	a81-a1	a4	a81-a4	a7	a81-a7	a81-a22	a22	a81-a54	a54
a78	a81-a78	a38	a81-a38	a2	a81-a2	$2*a81-a4-a5-a6$	$a4+a5+a6-a81$	a8	a81-a8	a81-a23	a23	a81-a55	a55
a77	a81-a77	a37	a81-a37	a3	a81-a3	a5	a81-a5	$2*a81-a7-a8-a9$	$a7+a8+a9-a81$	a81-a24	a24	a81-a56	a56
a76	a81-a76	a36	a81-a36	$2*a81-a1-a2-a3$	$a1+a2+a3-a81$	a6	a81-a6	a9	a81-a9	a81-a25	a25	a81-a57	a57
a75	a81-a75	a35	a81-a35	$a81-a7+a8-a5+a6-a10$	a81-a10	a81-a11	$a7-a8+2*a10+a11+2*a12-a1+a2-2*a81$	a81-a12	$a81+a1-a2+a5-a6-a12$	a81-a26	a26	a81-a58	a58
a74	a81-a74	a34	a81-a34	$a7-a8+a5-a6+a10$	a10	a11	$3*a81-a7+a8-2*a10-a11-2*a12+a1-a2$	a12	$a2-a5+a6+a12-a1$	$a22+a23+a24+a25+a26-2*a81$	$3*a81-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26$	a81-a59	a59
a73	a81-a73	$a81+a21-a20-a33$	a81-a33	$a20+2*a33+a32+a31+a30+a29+a28+2*a27-a13+a14-4*a81-a21$	a81-a32	a81-a31	a81-a30	a81-a29	a81-a28	a81-a27	$a81+a13-a14-a27$	a81-a60	a60
a72	a81-a72	$a20+a33-a21$	a33	$5*a81+a21-a20-2*a33-a32-a31-a30-a29-a28-2*a27+a13-a14$	a32	a31	a30	a29	a28	a27	$a14+a27-a13$	$a52+a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59+a60-4*a81$	$5*a81-a52-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59-a60$
$a81+a51-a50-a71$	a81-a71	$a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a69+a70+2*a71+2*a61-a51+a50+a40-a39-6*a81$	a81-a70	a81-a69	a81-a68	a81-a67	a81-a66	a81-a65	a81-a64	a81-a63	a81-a62	a81-a61	$a81+a39-a40-a61$
$a50+a71-a51$	a71	$7*a81-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a69-a70-2*a71-2*a61+a51-a50-a40+a39$	a70	a69	a68	a67	a66	a65	a64	a63	a62	a61	$a40+a61-a39$

• Details

It is an **algebraic flat striped** magic square of order 14 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×14 and two magic rectangles of order 2×10 embedded with a magic square of order 10. It is again composed two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×10 and two magic rectangles of order 2×6 embedded with a magic square of order 6. It is again composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 and one magic rectangle of order 2×6 . In this case the magic sums are , $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.17. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 14 based on Result 2.15 are given by

14	mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	567								
39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	-18	50	51	567
42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	99	31	30	567
-279	360	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	252	20	21	29	52	567
80	1	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	-171	61	60	28	53	567
79	2	63	18	1	80	4	77	7	74	59	22	27	54	567
78	3	38	43	2	79	147	-66	8	73	58	23	26	55	567
77	4	37	44	3	78	5	76	138	-57	57	24	25	56	567
76	5	36	45	156	-75	6	75	9	72	56	25	24	57	567
75	6	35	46	73	71	70	-107	69	67	55	26	23	58	567
74	7	34	47	8	10	11	188	12	14	-42	123	22	59	567
73	8	49	48	-54	49	50	51	52	53	54	53	21	60	567
72	9	32	33	135	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	180	-99	567
11	10	372	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	19	567
70	71	-291	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	567
567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567

14	mgc	14x14	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	©IJT	616								
39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	31	50	51	616
49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	57	38	37	616
-244	332	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	287	20	21	36	52	616
80	8	75	74	73	72	71	70	69	-199	68	67	35	53	616
79	9	84	4	1	87	4	84	7	81	66	22	34	54	616
78	10	38	50	2	86	161	-73	8	80	65	23	33	55	616
77	11	37	51	3	85	5	83	152	-64	64	24	32	56	616
76	12	36	52	170	-82	6	82	9	79	63	25	31	57	616
75	13	35	53	80	78	77	-121	76	74	62	26	30	58	616
74	14	34	54	8	10	11	209	12	14	-56	144	29	59	616
73	15	56	55	-82	56	57	58	59	60	61	60	28	60	616
72	16	32	33	170	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	152	-64	616
18	17	330	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	26	616
70	71	-242	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	616
616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616	616

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 243, S_{10 \times 10} := 405, S_{14 \times 14} := 567$ and $m := 81$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 248, S_{10 \times 10} := 440, S_{14 \times 14} := 616$ and $m := 88$.

2.6.3 Cornered

Result 2.16. *An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 14 is given by*

$a4-2^*a2-a3+2^*m-a1$	a1	a2	$a2+a3-a4$	a5	m-a5	m-a11	a11	m-a21	a21	m-a35	a35	m-a53	a53
$a1-a4+2^*a2+a3-m$	m-a1	m-a2	$a4-a2-a3+m$	a6	m-a6	m-a12	a12	m-a22	a22	m-a36	a36	m-a54	a54
a3	a4	$a1-a4+a2$	$2^*m-a3-a1-a2$	a7	m-a7	m-a13	a13	m-a23	a23	m-a37	a37	m-a55	a55
m-a3	m-a4	m-a1+a4-a2	$a3+a1+a2-m$	$2^*m-a5-a6-a7$	$a5+a6+a7-m$	m-a14	a14	m-a24	a24	m-a38	a38	m-a56	a56
$3^*m-a5+a6-a3-2^*a1-2^*a2+a4-a8$	m-a8	m-a9	$a5-a6+a3+2^*a1+2^*a2-a4+2^*a8+a9+2^*a10-4^*m$	m-a10	m-a10	m-a15	a15	m-a25	a25	m-a39	a39	m-a57	a57
$a5-a6+a3+2^*a1+2^*a2-a4+a8-2^*m$	a8	a9	$5^*m-a5+a6-a3-2^*a1-2^*a2+a4-2^*a8-a9-2^*a10$	a10	a10	$a11+a12+a13+a14+a15-2^*m$	$3^*m-a11-a12-a13-a14-a15$	m-a26	a26	m-a40	a40	m-a58	a58
$a11-a12-2^*a7-2^*a6+a3+2^*a1+2^*a2-a4+2^*a8+2^*a9+2^*a10-a16-2^*m$	m-a16	m-a17	m-a18	m-a19	$2^*a16-a11+a12+2^*a20+a19-2^*a10-2^*a9-2^*a8+a4-a3+a18+2^*a7+a17+2^*a6-2^*a2-2^*a1$	m-a20	m-a20	m-a27	a27	m-a41	a41	m-a59	a59
$3^*m-a11+a12+2^*a7+2^*a6-a3-2^*a1-2^*a2+a4-2^*a8-2^*a9-2^*a10+a16$	a16	a17	a18	a19	$m-2^*a16+a11-a12-2^*a20-a19+2^*a10+2^*a9+2^*a8-a4+a3-a18-2^*a7-a17-2^*a6+2^*a2+2^*a1$	a20	a20	$a21+a22+a23+a24+a25+a26+a27-3^*m$	$4^*m-a21-a22-a23-a24-a25-a26-a27$	m-a42	a42	m-a60	a60
$m+a21-a22+a13-a14-a18+a17-a28$	m-a28	m-a29	m-a30	m-a31	m-a32	m-a33	$a18-a17-a13+a14+2^*a34+a33+a32+a31+a30+a29+2^*a28+a22-a21-4^*m$	m-a34	m-a34	m-a43	a43	m-a61	a61
$a22-a13+a14+a18-a17+a28-a21$	a28	a29	a30	a31	a32	a33	$a18+a17+a13-a14-2^*a34-a33-a32-a31-a30-a29-2^*a28-a22+a21-5^*m$	a34	a34	$a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a41+a42+a43-4^*m$	$5^*m-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a41-a42-a43$	m-a62	a62
$2^*a7+2^*a6-2^*a8-2^*a10-2^*a9+2^*a20+2^*a19+2^*a16+2^*a12+2^*a15+a35+a18+a17+a13+a14-a3+a4-a30+a29-a36+a23-a24-3^*m-a44-2^*a2-2^*a1$	m-a44	$2^*a44+2^*a2+2^*a1-2^*a7-2^*a6+2^*a8+2^*a10+2^*a9-2^*a20-2^*a19-2^*a16-2^*a12-2^*a15-a35-a18-a17-a13-a14+a3-a4+a30-a29+a36+a23-a24-3^*m-a44-2^*a2-2^*a1$	m-a46	m-a45	m-a48	m-a49	m-a50	m-a51	m-a47	m-a52	m-a52	m-a63	a63
$a44+2^*a2+2^*a1-2^*a7-2^*a6+2^*a8+2^*a10+2^*a9-2^*a20-2^*a19-2^*a16-2^*a12-2^*a15-a35-a18-a17-a13-a14+a3-a4+a30-a29+a36-a23+a24+4^*m$	a44	$2^*a7+2^*a6-2^*a8-2^*a10-2^*a9+2^*a20+2^*a19+2^*a16+2^*a12+2^*a15+a35+a18+a17+a13+a14-a3+a4-a30+a29-a36-a50-a51-2^*a52-a45-a46-a47-a48-a49+a23-a24+2^*m-2^*a44-2^*a2-2^*a1$	a46	a45	a48	a49	a50	a51	a47	a52	a52	$a53+a54+a55+a56+a57+a58+a59+a60+a61+a62+a63-5^*m$	$6^*m-a53-a54-a55-a56-a57-a58-a59-a60-a61-a62-a63$
$a37+a53-a54+a25+a35+a31-a26-a49+a23-a24-a45-2^*a46-a47-a48-a50-a51-2^*a52+a4-a30+a29+a17+a13+a14-a3+2^*a15+a18+2^*a19+2^*a16+2^*a12-2^*a9+2^*a20+2^*a6-2^*a8-2^*a10+2^*a7-2^*a44-2^*a2-2^*a1-a32+3^*m-a64-a38-a36$	m-a64	m-a65	m-a66	m-a67	m-a68	m-a69	m-a70	m-a71	m-a72	m-a73	$2^*a64+a68+a38+a36-a37+a67-a53+a54-a25+a73+a72+a71-a35+a69+a70-a31+a26+a49-a23+a24+a45+2^*a46+a47+a48+a50+a51+2^*a52-a4+a30-a29-a17-a13-a14+a3-2^*a15-a18-2^*a19-2^*a16-2^*a12+2^*a9-2^*a20-2^*a6+2^*a8+2^*a10-2^*a7+2^*a44+2^*a2+2^*a74+2^*a1+a32-8^*m+a66+a65$	m-a74	m-a74
$a64+a38+a36-a37-a53+a54-a25-a35-a31+a26+a49-a23+a24+a45+2^*a46+a47+a48+a50+a51+2^*a52-a4+a30-a29-a17-a13-a14+a3-2^*a15-a18-2^*a19-2^*a16-2^*a12+2^*a9-2^*a20-2^*a6+2^*a8+2^*a10-2^*a7+2^*a44+2^*a2+2^*a1+a32-2^*m$	a64	a65	a66	a67	a68	a69	a70	a71	a72	a73	$a37-a67+a53-a54+a25-a73-a72-a71+a35-a69-a70+a31-a26-a49-a23-a24-a45-2^*a46-a47-a48-a50-a51-2^*a52+a4-a30+a29+a17+a13+a14-a3+2^*a15+a18+2^*a19+2^*a16+2^*a12-2^*a9+2^*a20+2^*a6-2^*a8-2^*a10+2^*a7-2^*a44-2^*a2-2^*a74-2^*a1-a32+9^*m-a66-a65-2^*a64-a68-a38-a36$	a74	a74

• Details

It is an **algebraic cornered striped** magic square of order 14, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.18. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 14 based on Result 2.16 are given by

14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/												462	14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/												567		
	128	1	2	1	5	61	55	11	45	21	31	35	13	53	462		158	1	2	1	5	76	70	11	60	21	46	35	28	53	567
	-62	65	64	65	6	60	54	12	44	22	30	36	12	54	462		-77	80	79	80	6	75	69	12	59	22	45	36	27	54	567
	3	4	-1	126	7	59	53	13	43	23	29	37	11	55	462		3	4	-1	156	7	74	68	13	58	23	44	37	26	55	567
	63	62	67	-60	114	-48	52	14	42	24	28	38	10	56	462		78	77	82	-75	144	-63	67	14	57	24	43	38	25	56	567
	186	58	57	-215	56	56	51	15	41	25	27	39	9	57	462		231	73	72	-275	71	71	66	15	56	25	42	39	24	57	567
	-120	8	9	281	10	10	-67	133	40	26	26	40	8	58	462		-150	8	9	356	10	10	-97	178	55	26	41	40	23	58	567
	-116	50	49	48	47	94	46	46	39	27	25	41	7	59	462		-146	65	64	63	62	94	61	61	54	27	40	41	22	59	567
	182	16	17	18	19	-28	20	20	-30	96	24	42	6	60	462		227	16	17	18	19	-13	20	20	-75	156	39	42	21	60	567
	35	38	37	36	35	34	33	18	32	32	23	43	5	61	462		50	53	52	51	50	49	48	-42	47	47	38	43	20	61	567
	31	28	29	30	31	32	33	48	34	34	87	-21	4	62	462		31	28	29	30	31	32	33	123	34	34	27	54	19	62	567
	-52	22	272	20	21	18	17	16	15	19	14	14	3	63	462		-97	37	257	35	36	33	32	31	30	34	29	29	18	63	567
	118	44	-206	46	45	48	49	50	51	47	52	52	308	-242	462		178	44	-176	46	45	48	49	50	51	47	52	52	233	-152	567
	-254	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	757	-8	-8	462		-209	17	16	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	637	7	7	567
	320	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	-691	74	74	462		290	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	-556	74	74	567
	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462	462		567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567	567

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 132, S_{6 \times 6} := 198, S_{8 \times 8} := 264, S_{10 \times 10} := 330, S_{12 \times 12} := 396, S_{14 \times 14} := 462$ and $m := 53$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 162, S_{6 \times 6} := 243, S_{8 \times 8} := 244, S_{10 \times 10} := 405, S_{12 \times 12} := 486, S_{14 \times 14} := 567$ and $m = 81$.

2.7 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 16

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 16, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.7.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.17. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 16 in cyclic way is given by*

a59	a60	a61	a62	a63	a64	a65	a66	a67	a68	a69	a70	a71	7*m-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-a69-a70-a71-a61-a59-a60	m-a72	a72
m-a59	m-a60	m-a61	m-a62	m-a63	m-a64	m-a65	m-a66	m-a67	m-a68	m-a69	m-a70	m-a71	a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+a69+a70+a71+a61+a59+a60-6*m	m-a73	a73
7*m-a99-a98-2*a97+a72-a73-a101-a105-a104-a103-a102-a108-a107-a106-a100	a99+a98+2*a97-a72+a73+a101+a105+a104+a103+a102+a108+a107+a106+a100-6*m	a25	a26	a27	a28	a29	a30	a31	a32	a33	5*m-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33	m-a34	a34	m-a74	a74
a108	m-a108	m-a25	m-a26	m-a27	m-a28	m-a29	m-a30	m-a31	m-a32	m-a33	a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33-4*m	m-a35	a35	m-a75	a75
a107	m-a107	5*m-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-2*a51+a34-a35	a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+2*a51-a34+a35-4*m	a7	a8	a9	a10	a11	3*m-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11	m-a12	a12	m-a36	a36	m-a76	a76
a106	m-a106	a58	m-a58	m-a7	m-a8	m-a9	m-a10	m-a11	a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-2*m	m-a13	a13	m-a37	a37	m-a77	a77
a105	m-a105	a57	m-a57	3*m-a24-a23-a22-2*a21+a12-a13	a24+a23+a22+2*a21-a12+a13-2*m	a4-2*a2-a3+2*m-a1	a1	a2	a2+a3-a4	m-a14	a14	m-a38	a38	m-a78	a78
a104	m-a104	a56	m-a56	a24	m-a24	a1-a4+2*a2+a3-m	m-a1	m-a2	a4-a2-a3+m	m-a15	a15	m-a39	a39	m-a79	a79
a103	m-a103	a55	m-a55	a23	m-a23	a3	a4	a1-a4+a2	2*m-a3-a1-a2	m-a16	a16	m-a40	a40	m-a80	a80
a102	m-a102	a54	m-a54	a22	m-a22	m-a3	m-a4	m-a1+a4-a2	a3+a1+a2-m	a12+a13+a14+a15+a16-2*m	3*m-a12-a13-a14-a15-a16	m-a41	a41	m-a81	a81
a101	m-a101	a53	m-a53	a21	m-a21	a20+a19+a18+2*a17-a7+a8-2*m	m-a20	m-a19	m-a18	m-a17	m+a7-a8-a17	m-a42	a42	m-a82	a82
a100	m-a100	a52	m-a52	a13+a21-a12	m+a12-a13-a21	3*m-a20-a19-a18-2*a17+a7-a8	a20	a19	a18	a17	a8+a17-a7	a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40+a41+a42-4*m	5*m-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40-a41-a42	m-a83	a83
a99	m-a99	a51	m-a51	a50+a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+2*a43-a25+a26-4*m	m-a50	m-a49	m-a48	m-a47	m-a46	m-a45	m-a44	m-a43	m+a25-a26-a43	m-a84	a84
a98	m-a98	a35+a51-a34	m+a34-a35-a51	5*m-a50-a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-2*a43+a25-a26	a50	a49	a48	a47	a46	a45	a44	a43	a26+a43-a25	a72+a74+a73+a75+a84+a82+a83+a81+a77+a76+a78+a80+a79-6*m	7*m-a72-a74-a73-a75-a84-a82-a83-a81-a77-a76-a78-a80-a79
a97	m-a97	a96+a88+a87+2*a85+a86+a95+a94+a93+a92+a91+a90+a89-a59+a60-6*m	m-a96	m-a95	m-a94	m-a93	m-a92	m-a91	m-a90	m-a89	m-a88	m-a87	m-a86	m-a85	m+a59-a60-a85
a73+a97-a72	m+a72-a73-a97	7*m-a96-a88-a87-2*a85-a86-a95-a94-a93-a92-a91-a90-a89+a59-a60	a96	a95	a94	a93	a92	a91	a90	a89	a88	a87	a86	a85	a60+a85-a59

• Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic striped** magic square of order 16 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×14 embedded with a magic square of order 12. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×10 embedded with a magic square of order 8. It is again composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×6 embedded with a magic square of order 4. This magic square of order 4 is with equal sums two magic rectangles of order 2×4 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.19. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 16 based on Result 2.17 are given by

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/												https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/		©IJT	872
	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	-82	37	72	872
	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	191	36	73	872
	-565	674	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	284	75	34	35	74	872
	108	1	84	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	-175	74	35	34	75	872
	107	2	57	52	7	8	9	10	11	282	97	12	73	36	33	76	872
	106	3	58	51	102	101	100	99	98	-173	96	13	72	37	32	77	872
	105	4	57	52	215	-106	214	1	2	1	95	14	71	38	31	78	872
	104	5	56	53	24	85	-105	108	107	108	94	15	70	39	30	79	872
	103	6	55	54	23	86	3	4	-1	212	93	16	69	40	29	80	872
	102	7	54	55	22	87	106	105	110	-103	-148	257	68	41	28	81	872
	101	8	53	56	21	88	-126	89	90	91	92	91	67	42	27	82	872
	100	9	52	57	22	87	235	20	19	18	17	18	-94	203	26	83	872
	99	10	51	58	-20	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	65	25	84	872
	98	11	52	57	129	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	44	360	-251	872
	97	12	518	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	23	872
	98	11	-409	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	86	872
	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872	872

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/												https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/		©IJT	976
	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	9	50	72	976
	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	113	49	73	976
	-474	596	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	349	88	34	48	74	976
	108	14	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	-227	87	35	47	75	976
	107	15	122	0	7	8	9	10	11	321	110	12	86	36	46	76	976
	106	16	58	64	115	114	113	112	111	-199	109	13	85	37	45	77	976
	105	17	57	65	254	-132	240	1	2	1	108	14	84	38	44	78	976
	104	18	56	66	24	98	-118	121	120	121	107	15	83	39	43	79	976
	103	19	55	67	23	99	3	4	-1	238	106	16	82	40	42	80	976
	102	20	54	68	22	100	119	118	123	-116	-174	296	81	41	41	81	976
	101	21	53	69	21	101	-152	102	103	104	105	104	80	42	40	82	976
	100	22	52	70	22	100	274	20	19	18	17	18	-146	268	39	83	976
	99	23	51	71	-72	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	78	38	84	976
	98	24	52	70	194	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	44	282	-160	976
	97	25	440	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	36	976
	98	24	-318	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	86	976
	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976	976

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 218, S_{8 \times 8} := 436, S_{12 \times 12} := 654, S_{16 \times 16} := 872$ and $m := 109$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 244, S_{8 \times 8} := 488, S_{12 \times 12} := 732, S_{16 \times 16} := 976$ and $m := 122$.

2.7.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.18. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 16 in flat way is given by*

a57	a58	a59	a60	a61	a62	a63	a64	a65	a66	a67	a68	a69	$8*m-a62-a63-a64-a65-a66-a67-a68-2*a69-a70-a61-a59-a60-a57-a58$	a69	a70
m-a57	m-a58	m-a59	m-a60	m-a61	m-a62	m-a63	m-a64	m-a65	m-a66	m-a67	m-a68	m-a69	$a62+a63+a64+a65+a66+a67+a68+2*a69+a70+a61+a59+a60+a57+a58-7*m$	m-a69	m-a70
$6*m-a105-a104-a103-a102-a101-a100-a99-a98-a97-a96-a95$	$a105+a104+a103+a102+a101+a100+a99+a98+a97+a96+a95-5*m$	a23	a24	a25	a26	a27	a28	a29	a30	a31	$6*m-a23-a24-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32-a33$	a32	a33	m-a71	a71
a105	m-a105	m-a23	m-a24	m-a25	m-a26	m-a27	m-a28	m-a29	m-a30	m-a31	$a23+a24+a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32+a33-5*m$	m-a32	m-a33	m-a72	a72
a104	m-a104	$4*m-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-a51-a50$	$a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+a51+a50-3*m$	a5	a6	a7	a8	a9	$4*m-a5-a6-a7-a8-a9-a10-a11$	a10	a11	m-a34	a34	m-a73	a73
a103	m-a103	a56	m-a56	m-a5	m-a6	m-a7	m-a8	m-a9	$a5+a6+a7+a8+a9+a10+a11-3*m$	m-a10	m-a11	m-a35	a35	m-a74	a74
a102	m-a102	a55	m-a55	$2*m-a20-a21-a22$	$a20+a21+a22-m$	$a4-2*a2-a3+2*m-a1$	$a1-a4+2*a2+a3-m$	a3	m-a3	m-a12	a12	m-a36	a36	m-a75	a75
a101	m-a101	a54	m-a54	a22	m-a22	a1	m-a1	a4	m-a4	m-a13	a13	m-a37	a37	m-a76	a76
a100	m-a100	a53	m-a53	a21	m-a21	a2	m-a2	$a1-a4+a2$	$m-a1+a4-a2$	m-a14	a14	m-a38	a38	m-a77	a77
a99	m-a99	a52	m-a52	a20	m-a20	$a2+a3-a4$	$a4-a2-a3+m$	$2*m-a3-a1-a2$	$a3+a1+a2-m$	$a12+a13+a14-m$	$2*m-a12-a13-a14$	m-a39	a39	m-a78	a78
a98	m-a98	a51	m-a51	$a11-a10+a19$	a19	$4*m-a11+a10-2*a19-a18-a17-a16-2*a15-a5+a6$	a18	a17	a16	a15	$a5-a6+a15$	m-a40	a40	m-a79	a79
a97	m-a97	a50	m-a50	$m-a11+a10-a19$	m-a19	$a19+a11-a10+a19+a18+a17+a16+2*a15+a5-a6-3*m$	m-a18	m-a17	m-a16	m-a15	$m-a5+a6-a15$	$a34+a35+a36+a37+a38+a39+a40-3*m$	$4*m-a34-a35-a36-a37-a38-a39-a40$	m-a80	a80
a96	m-a96	$m+a33-a32-a49$	m-a49	$a32+2*a49+a48+a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+2*a41-a23+a24-5*m-a33$	m-a48	m-a47	m-a46	m-a45	m-a44	m-a43	m-a42	m-a41	$m+a23-a24-a41$	m-a81	a81
a95	m-a95	$a32+a49-a33$	a49	$6*m+a33-a32-2*a49-a48-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-2*a41+a23-a24$	a48	a47	a46	a45	a44	a43	a42	a41	$a24+a41-a23$	$a71+a72+a73+a74+a75+a76+a77+a78+a79+a80+a81-5*m$	$6*m-a71-a72-a73-a74-a75-a76-a77-a78-a79-a80-a81$
$m+a70-a69-a94$	m-a94	$a69-a70+a88+a87+a85+a86+a84+2*a82+a83+2*a94+a93+a92+a91+a90+a89-a57+a58-7*m$	m-a93	m-a92	m-a91	m-a90	m-a89	m-a88	m-a87	m-a86	m-a85	m-a84	m-a83	m-a82	$m+a57-a58-a82$
$a69+a94-a70$	a94	$8*m-a69+a70-a88-a87-a85-a86-a84-2*a82-a83-2*a94-a93-a92-a91-a90-a89+a57-a58$	a93	a92	a91	a90	a89	a88	a87	a86	a85	a84	a83	a82	$a58+a82-a57$

• Details

It is an *algebraic flat-type striped magic square* of order 16 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×16 and two magic rectangles of order 2×12 embedded with a magic square of order 12. It is again composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×12 and two magic rectangles of order 2×8 embedded with a magic square of order 8. It is again composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and two magic rectangles of order 2×4 embedded with a magic square of order 4. It is again composed of two equal sums magic

rectangles of order 2×4 . In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.20. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 16 based on Result 2.18 are given by

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														808	
	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	-285	78	79	808
	35	34	33	32	31	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	386	23	22	808
	-593	694	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	199	41	42	21	80	808
	114	-13	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	-98	60	59	20	81	808
	113	-12	-30	131	14	15	16	17	18	285	19	20	58	43	19	82	808
	112	-11	65	36	87	86	85	84	83	-184	82	81	57	44	18	83	808
	111	-10	64	37	112	-11	171	-70	12	89	80	21	56	45	17	84	808
	110	-9	63	38	31	70	10	91	13	88	79	22	55	46	16	85	808
	109	-8	62	39	30	71	11	90	8	93	78	23	54	47	15	86	808
	108	-7	61	40	29	72	10	91	169	-68	-35	136	53	48	14	87	808
	107	-6	60	41	29	28	222	27	26	25	24	23	52	49	13	88	808
	106	-5	59	42	72	73	-121	74	75	76	77	78	19	82	12	89	808
	105	-4	44	43	89	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	50	11	90	808
	104	-3	57	58	12	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	51	430	-329	808
	-1	-2	748	-1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	9	808
	102	103	-647	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	92	808
	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808	808

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														944	
	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	-149	78	79	944
	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	267	40	39	944
	-491	609	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	301	41	42	38	80	944
	114	4	86	85	84	83	82	81	80	79	78	-183	77	76	37	81	944
	113	5	38	80	14	15	16	17	18	353	19	20	75	43	36	82	944
	112	6	65	53	104	103	102	101	100	-235	99	98	74	44	35	83	944
	111	7	64	54	146	-28	205	-87	12	106	97	21	73	45	34	84	944
	110	8	63	55	31	87	10	108	13	105	96	22	72	46	33	85	944
	109	9	62	56	30	88	11	107	8	110	95	23	71	47	32	86	944
	108	10	61	57	29	89	10	108	203	-85	-52	170	70	48	31	87	944
	107	11	60	58	29	28	290	27	26	25	24	23	69	49	30	88	944
	106	12	59	59	89	90	-172	91	92	93	94	95	-32	150	29	89	944
	105	13	61	60	4	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	67	28	90	944
	104	14	57	58	114	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	51	345	-227	944
	16	15	629	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	26	944
	102	103	-511	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	92	944
	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944	944

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 202, S_{8 \times 8} := 404, S_{12 \times 12} := 606, S_{16 \times 16} := 808$ and $m := 101$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 236, S_{8 \times 8} := 472, S_{12 \times 12} := 708, S_{16 \times 16} := 944$ and $m := 118$.

2.7.3 Cornered

Result 2.19. *An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 16 is given by*

$a_4-2^2a_2-a_3+2^2m-a_1$	a_1	a_2	$a_2+a_3-a_4$	a_5	$m-a_5$	$m-a_{11}$	a_{11}	$m-a_{21}$	a_{21}	$m-a_{35}$	a_{35}	$m-a_{53}$	a_{53}	$m-a_{75}$	a_{75}
$a_1-a_4+2^2a_2+a_3-m$	$m-a_1$	$m-a_2$	$a_4-a_2-a_3+m$	a_6	$m-a_6$	$m-a_{12}$	a_{12}	$m-a_{22}$	a_{22}	$m-a_{36}$	a_{36}	$m-a_{54}$	a_{54}	$m-a_{76}$	a_{76}
a_3	a_4	$a_1-a_4+a_2$	$2^2m-a_3-a_1-a_2$	a_7	$m-a_7$	$m-a_{13}$	a_{13}	$m-a_{23}$	a_{23}	$m-a_{37}$	a_{37}	$m-a_{55}$	a_{55}	$m-a_{77}$	a_{77}
$m-a_3$	$m-a_4$	$m-a_1+a_4-a_2$	$a_3+a_1+a_2-m$	$2^2m-a_5-a_6-a_7$	$a_5+a_6+a_7-m$	$m-a_{14}$	a_{14}	$m-a_{24}$	a_{24}	$m-a_{38}$	a_{38}	$m-a_{56}$	a_{56}	$m-a_{78}$	a_{78}
$3^2m-a_5+a_6-a_3-2^2a_1-2^2a_2+a_4-a_8$	$m-a_8$	$m-a_9$	$a_5-a_6+a_3+2^2a_1+2^2a_2-a_4+2^2a_8+a_9+2^2a_{10}-4^2m$	$m-a_{10}$	$m-a_{10}$	$m-a_{15}$	a_{15}	$m-a_{25}$	a_{25}	$m-a_{39}$	a_{39}	$m-a_{57}$	a_{57}	$m-a_{79}$	a_{79}
$a_5-a_6+a_3+2^2a_1+2^2a_2-a_4+a_8-2^2m$	a_8	a_9	$5^2m-a_5+a_6-a_3-2^2a_1-2^2a_2+a_4-2^2a_8-a_9-2^2a_{10}$	a_{10}	a_{10}	$a_{11}+a_{12}+a_{13}+a_{14}+a_{15}-2^2m$	$3^2m-a_{11}-a_{12}-a_{13}-a_{14}-a_{15}$	$m-a_{26}$	a_{26}	$m-a_{40}$	a_{40}	$m-a_{58}$	a_{58}	$m-a_{80}$	a_{80}
$a_{11}-a_{12}-2^2a_7-2^2a_6+a_3+2^2a_1+2^2a_2-a_4+2^2a_8+2^2a_9+2^2a_{10}-a_{16}-2^2m$	$m-a_{16}$	$m-a_{17}$	$m-a_{18}$	$m-a_{19}$	$2^2a_{16}-a_{11}+a_{12}+2^2a_{20}+a_{19}-2^2a_{10}-2^2a_9-2^2a_8+a_4-a_3+a_{18}+2^2a_7+a_{17}+2^2a_6-2^2a_2-2^2a_1$	$m-a_{20}$	$m-a_{20}$	$m-a_{27}$	a_{27}	$m-a_{41}$	a_{41}	$m-a_{59}$	a_{59}	$m-a_{81}$	a_{81}
$3^2m-a_{11}+a_{12}+2^2a_7+2^2a_6-a_3-2^2a_1-2^2a_2+a_4-2^2a_8-2^2a_9-2^2a_{10}+a_{16}$	a_{16}	a_{17}	a_{18}	a_{19}	$m-2^2a_{16}+a_{11}-a_{12}-2^2a_{20}-a_{19}+2^2a_{10}+2^2a_9+2^2a_8-a_4+a_3-a_{18}-2^2a_7-a_{17}+2^2a_6+2^2a_2+2^2a_1$	a_{20}	a_{20}	$a_{21}+a_{22}+a_{23}+a_{24}+a_{25}+a_{26}+a_{27}-3^2m$	$4^2m-a_{21}-a_{22}-a_{23}-a_{24}-a_{25}-a_{26}-a_{27}$	$m-a_{42}$	a_{42}	$m-a_{60}$	a_{60}	$m-a_{82}$	a_{82}
$m+a_{21}-a_{22}+a_{13}-a_{14}-a_{18}+a_{17}-a_{28}$	$m-a_{28}$	$m-a_{29}$	$m-a_{30}$	$m-a_{31}$	$m-a_{32}$	$m-a_{33}$	$a_{18}-a_{17}-a_{13}+a_{14}+2^2a_{34}+a_{33}+a_{32}+a_{31}+a_{30}+a_{29}+2^2a_{28}+a_{22}-a_{21}-4^2m$	$m-a_{34}$	$m-a_{34}$	$m-a_{43}$	a_{43}	$m-a_{61}$	a_{61}	$m-a_{83}$	a_{83}
$a_{22}-a_{13}+a_{14}+a_{18}-a_{17}+a_{28}-a_{21}$	a_{28}	a_{29}	a_{30}	a_{31}	a_{32}	a_{33}	$5^2m-a_{18}+a_{17}+a_{13}-a_{14}-2^2a_{34}-a_{33}-a_{32}-a_{31}-a_{30}-a_{29}-2^2a_{28}-a_{22}+a_{21}$	a_{34}	a_{34}	$a_{35}+a_{36}+a_{37}+a_{38}+a_{39}+a_{40}+a_{41}+a_{42}+a_{43}-4^2m$	$5^2m-a_{35}-a_{36}-a_{37}-a_{38}-a_{39}-a_{40}-a_{41}-a_{42}-a_{43}$	$m-a_{62}$	a_{62}	$m-a_{84}$	a_{84}
$2^2a_7+2^2a_6-2^2a_8-2^2a_{10}-2^2a_9+2^2a_{20}+2^2a_{19}+2^2a_{16}+2^2a_{12}+2^2a_{15}+a_{35}+a_{18}+a_{17}+a_{13}+a_{14}-a_3+a_4-a_{30}+a_{29}-a_{36}+a_{23}-a_{24}-3^2m-a_{44}-2^2a_2-2^2a_1$	$m-a_{44}$	$m-a_{45}$	$m-a_{46}$	$m-a_{47}$	$m-a_{48}$	$m-a_{49}$	$m-a_{50}$	$m-a_{51}$	$2^2a_{44}+2^2a_2+2^2a_1-2^2a_7-2^2a_6+2^2a_8+2^2a_{10}+2^2a_9-2^2a_{20}-2^2a_{19}-2^2a_{16}-2^2a_{12}-2^2a_{15}-a_{35}-a_{18}-a_{17}-a_{13}-a_{14}+a_3-a_4+a_{30}-a_{29}+a_{36}+a_{50}+a_{51}+2^2a_{52}+a_{45}+a_{46}+a_{47}+a_{48}+a_{49}-a_{23}+a_{24}-m$	$m-a_{52}$	$m-a_{52}$	$m-a_{63}$	a_{63}	$m-a_{85}$	a_{85}
$a_{44}+2^2a_2+2^2a_1-2^2a_7-2^2a_6+2^2a_8+2^2a_{10}+2^2a_9-2^2a_{20}-2^2a_{19}-2^2a_{16}-2^2a_{12}-2^2a_{15}-a_{35}-a_{18}-a_{17}-a_{13}-a_{14}+a_3-a_4+a_{30}-a_{29}+a_{36}-a_{23}+a_{24}+4^2m$	a_{44}	a_{45}	a_{46}	a_{47}	a_{48}	a_{49}	a_{50}	a_{51}	$2^2a_7+2^2a_6-2^2a_8-2^2a_{10}-2^2a_9+2^2a_{20}+2^2a_{19}+2^2a_{16}+2^2a_{12}+2^2a_{15}+a_{35}+a_{18}+a_{17}+a_{13}+a_{14}-a_3-a_4-a_{30}+a_{29}-a_{36}-a_{50}-a_{51}-2^2a_{52}-a_{45}-a_{46}-a_{47}-a_{48}-a_{49}+a_{23}-a_{24}+2^2m-2^2a_{44}-2^2a_2-2^2a_1$	$m-a_{52}$	a_{52}	$a_{53}+a_{54}+a_{55}+a_{56}+a_{57}+a_{58}+a_{59}+a_{60}+a_{61}+a_{62}+a_{63}-5^2m$	$6^2m-a_{53}-a_{54}-a_{55}-a_{56}-a_{57}-a_{58}-a_{59}-a_{60}-a_{61}-a_{62}-a_{63}$	$m-a_{86}$	a_{86}
$m+a_{53}-a_{54}+a_{37}-a_{38}+a_{25}-a_{26}-a_{32}+a_{31}-a_{46}+a_{45}-a_{64}$	$m-a_{64}$	$m-a_{65}$	$m-a_{66}$	$m-a_{67}$	$m-a_{68}$	$m-a_{69}$	$m-a_{70}$	$m-a_{71}$	$m-a_{72}$	$m-a_{73}$	$2^2a_{64}+a_{65}+a_{66}+a_{67}+a_{68}+a_{69}+a_{70}+a_{72}+2^2a_{74}+a_{73}+a_{71}+a_{32}-a_{31}+a_{26}+a_{46}-a_{45}-a_{25}+a_{54}-a_{53}-a_{37}+a_{38}-6^2m$	$m-a_{74}$	$m-a_{74}$	$m-a_{87}$	a_{87}
$a_{54}-a_{37}+a_{38}-a_{25}+a_{26}+a_{32}-a_{31}+a_{46}-a_{45}+a_{64}-a_{53}$	a_{64}	a_{65}	a_{66}	a_{67}	a_{68}	a_{69}	a_{70}	a_{71}	a_{72}	a_{73}	$7^2m-2^2a_{64}-a_{65}-a_{66}-a_{67}-a_{68}-a_{69}-a_{70}-a_{72}-2^2a_{74}-a_{73}-a_{71}-a_{32}+a_{31}-a_{26}-a_{46}+a_{45}+a_{25}-a_{54}+a_{53}+a_{37}-a_{38}$	a_{74}	a_{74}	$a_{75}+a_{87}+a_{85}+a_{86}+a_{84}+a_{82}+a_{83}+a_{81}+a_{77}+a_{76}+a_{78}+a_{80}+a_{79}-6^2m$	$7^2m-a_{75}-a_{87}-a_{85}-a_{86}-a_{84}-a_{82}-a_{83}-a_{81}-a_{77}-a_{76}-a_{78}-a_{80}-a_{79}$
$a_{24}+2^2a_{22}+a_{23}+2^2a_{27}+a_{65}-a_{66}-a_{88}+a_{75}-a_{17}-a_{13}+a_{14}+2^2a_{34}+a_{18}+a_{32}+a_{31}+a_{26}-a_{48}+a_{47}-a_{40}+a_{39}+a_{25}-a_{76}+a_{30}+a_{29}+2^2a_{28}+2^2a_{33}-a_{56}+a_{55}-8^2m$	$m-a_{88}$	$m-a_{89}$	$m-a_{90}$	$m-a_{91}$	$m-a_{92}$	$m-a_{93}$	$m-a_{94}$	$m-a_{95}$	$m-a_{96}$	$m-a_{97}$	$m-a_{98}$	$m-a_{99}$	$a_{99}+a_{98}+a_{97}+a_{96}-a_{65}+a_{66}+2^2a_{88}-a_{75}+a_{95}+a_{94}+a_{93}+a_{92}+2^2a_{100}+a_{91}+a_{90}+a_{89}+a_{17}+a_{13}-a_{14}-2^2a_{34}-a_{18}-a_{32}-a_{31}-a_{26}+a_{48}-a_{47}+a_{40}-a_{39}-a_{25}+a_{76}-a_{30}-a_{29}-2^2a_{28}-2^2a_{33}+a_{56}-a_{55}+2^2m-a_{24}-2^2a_{22}-a_{23}-2^2a_{27}$	$m-a_{100}$	$m-a_{100}$
$a_{66}+a_{88}-a_{75}+a_{17}+a_{13}-a_{14}-2^2a_{34}-a_{18}-a_{32}-a_{31}-a_{26}+a_{48}-a_{47}+a_{40}-a_{39}-a_{25}+a_{76}-a_{30}-a_{29}-2^2a_{28}-2^2a_{33}+a_{56}-a_{55}+9^2m-a_{24}-2^2a_{22}-a_{23}-2^2a_{27}-a_{65}$	a_{88}	a_{89}	a_{90}	a_{91}	a_{92}	a_{93}	a_{94}	a_{95}	a_{96}	a_{97}	a_{98}	a_{99}	a_{100}	a_{100}	a_{100}

• Details

It is an algebraic cornered striped magic square of order 16, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 and 14 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$ and $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$, where m is the width of the strip. See below two examples:

Example 2.21. Below are two examples of algebraic striped magic square of order 16 based on Result 2.19 are given by

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	704						
	170	1	4	1	13	75	57	31	27	61	-15	103	-69	157	-135	223	704
	-82	87	84	87	16	72	54	34	24	64	-18	106	-72	160	-138	226	704
	7	10	-5	164	19	69	51	37	21	67	-21	109	-75	163	-141	229	704
	81	78	93	-76	128	-40	48	40	18	70	-24	112	-78	166	-144	232	704
	238	66	63	-223	60	60	45	43	15	73	-27	115	-81	169	-147	235	704
	-150	22	25	311	28	28	9	79	12	76	-30	118	-84	172	-150	238	704
	-138	42	39	36	33	280	30	30	9	79	-33	121	-87	175	-153	241	704
	226	46	49	52	55	-192	58	58	226	-138	-36	124	-90	178	-156	244	704
	-3	6	3	0	-3	-6	-9	476	-12	-12	-39	127	-93	181	-159	247	704
	91	82	85	88	91	94	97	-388	100	100	683	-595	-96	184	-162	250	704
	160	-42	-45	-48	-51	-54	-57	-60	-63	920	-66	-66	-99	187	-165	253	704
	-72	130	133	136	139	142	145	148	151	-832	154	154	1452	-1364	-168	256	704
	-117	-102	-105	-108	-111	-114	-117	-120	-123	-126	-129	2152	-132	-132	-171	259	704
	205	190	193	196	199	202	205	208	211	214	217	-2064	220	220	2605	-2517	704
	513	-174	-177	-180	-183	-186	-189	-192	-195	-198	-201	-204	-207	2897	-210	-210	704
	-425	262	265	268	271	274	277	280	283	286	289	292	295	-2809	298	298	704
	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704	704

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	968						
	236	1	4	1	13	108	90	31	60	61	18	103	-36	157	-102	223	968
	-115	120	117	120	16	105	87	34	57	64	15	106	-39	160	-105	226	968
	7	10	-5	230	19	102	84	37	54	67	12	109	-42	163	-108	229	968
	114	111	126	-109	194	-73	81	40	51	70	9	112	-45	166	-111	232	968
	337	99	96	-355	93	93	78	43	48	73	6	115	-48	169	-114	235	968
	-216	22	25	476	28	28	-57	178	45	76	3	118	-51	172	-117	238	968
	-204	75	72	69	66	280	63	63	42	79	0	121	-54	175	-120	241	968
	325	46	49	52	55	-159	58	58	127	-6	-3	124	-57	178	-123	244	968
	30	39	36	33	30	27	24	344	21	21	-6	127	-60	181	-126	247	968
	91	82	85	88	91	94	97	-223	100	100	551	-430	-63	184	-129	250	968
	61	-9	-12	-15	-18	-21	-24	-27	-30	887	-33	-33	-66	187	-132	253	968
	60	130	133	136	139	142	145	148	151	-766	154	154	1287	-1166	-135	256	968
	-84	-69	-72	-75	-78	-81	-84	-87	-90	-93	-96	1954	-99	-99	-138	259	968
	205	190	193	196	199	202	205	208	211	214	217	-1833	220	220	2407	-2286	968
	249	-141	-144	-147	-150	-153	-156	-159	-162	-165	-168	-171	-174	2963	-177	-177	968
	-128	262	265	268	271	274	277	280	283	286	289	292	295	-2842	298	298	968
	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968	968

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 172, S_{6 \times 6} := 264, S_{8 \times 8} := 352, S_{10 \times 10} := 440, S_{12 \times 12} := 528, S_{14 \times 14} := 616, S_{16 \times 16} := 704$ and $m := 88$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 242, S_{6 \times 6} := 363, S_{8 \times 8} := 464, S_{10 \times 10} := 585, S_{12 \times 12} := 726, S_{14 \times 14} := 847, S_{16 \times 16} := 968$ and $m := 121$.

2.8 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 18

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 18, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.8.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.20. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 18 in cyclic way is given by*

a82	a83	a84	a85	a86	a87	a88	a89	a90	a91	a92	a93	a94	a95	a96	$8*m-a96-a95-a94-a93-a92-a91-a90-a89-a88-a87-a86-a85-a84-a83-a82$	m-a97	a97	
m-a82	m-a83	m-a84	m-a85	m-a86	m-a87	m-a88	m-a89	m-a90	m-a91	m-a92	m-a93	m-a94	m-a95	m-a96	$a96+a95+a94+a93+a92+a91+a90+a89+a88+a87+a86+a85+a84+a83+a82-7*m$	m-a98	a98	
$8*m-2*a126+a97-a128-a127-a133-a132-a131-a130-a129-a137-a136-a135-a134-a139-a138-a98$	$2*a126-a97+a128+a127+a133+a132+a131+a130+a129+a137+a136+a135+a134+a139+a138+a98-7*m$															m-a99	a99	
a139	m-a139																m-a100	a100
a138	m-a138																m-a101	a101
a137	m-a137																m-a102	a102
a136	m-a136																m-a103	a103
a135	m-a135																m-a104	a104
a134	m-a134																m-a105	a105
a133	m-a133																m-a106	a106
a132	m-a132																m-a107	a107
a131	m-a131																m-a108	a108
a130	m-a130																m-a109	a109
a129	m-a129																m-a110	a110
a128	m-a128																m-a111	a111
a127	m-a127																$a99+a97+a109+a110+a111+a105+a106+a107+a108+a100+a101+a102+a103+a104+a98-7*m$	$8*m-a99-a97-a109-a110-a111-a105-a106-a107-a108-a100-a101-a102-a103-a104-a98$
a126	m-a126	$a114+a113+a116+a115+a118+a117+a120+a119+a122+a121+a124+a123+a125+2*a112+a83-a82-7*m$	m-a125	m-a124	m-a123	m-a122	m-a121	m-a120	m-a119	m-a118	m-a117	m-a116	m-a115	m-a114	m-a113	m-a112	m+a82-a83-a112	
$a98+a126-a97$	$m+a97-a98-a126$	$8*m-a114-a113-a116-a115-a118-a117-a120-a119-a122-a121-a124-a123-a125-2*a112-a83+a82$	a125	a124	a123	a122	a121	a120	a119	a118	a117	a116	a115	a114	a113	a112	$a83+a112-a82$	

The internal part is exactly the same as given in Result 2.14.

• **Details**

It is an **algebraic cyclic striped** magic square of order 18 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. The internal part, i.e., magic square of order 14 is as given in Result 2.14. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 9m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.22. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 18 based on Result 2.23 are given by

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	1179												
	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	-287	34	97	1179
	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	418	33	98	1179
	-934	1065	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	291	80	51	32	99	1179
	139	-8	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	84	83	82	81	-160	79	52	31	100	1179
	138	-7	-52	183	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	405	110	21	78	53	30	101	1179
	137	-6	81	50	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	-274	109	22	77	54	29	102	1179
	136	-5	80	51	270	-139	378	1	2	3	4	5	108	23	76	55	28	103	1179
	135	-4	79	52	39	92	-247	130	129	128	127	126	107	24	75	56	27	104	1179
	134	-3	78	53	38	93	6	7	8	384	-21	9	106	25	74	57	26	105	1179
	133	-2	77	54	37	94	125	124	123	-253	152	122	105	26	73	58	25	106	1179
	132	-1	76	55	36	95	387	10	-40	11	12	13	104	27	72	59	24	107	1179
	131	0	75	56	35	96	-256	121	171	120	119	118	-225	356	71	60	23	108	1179
	130	1	74	57	34	97	-181	98	99	100	101	102	103	102	70	61	22	109	1179
	129	2	73	58	35	96	312	33	32	31	30	29	28	29	-39	170	21	110	1179
	128	3	72	59	73	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	68	20	111	1179
	127	4	73	58	58	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	643	-512	1179
	126	5	855	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	18	1179
	127	4	-724	125	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	113	1179
	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/		@IJTANEJA	©IJT	1332									
	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	-151	51	97	1332
	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	299	50	98	1332
	-798	946	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	393	97	51	49	99	1332
	139	9	108	107	106	105	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	-245	96	52	48	100	1332
	138	10	50	98	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	473	127	21	95	53	47	101	1332
	137	11	81	67	134	133	132	131	130	129	128	-325	126	22	94	54	46	102	1332
	136	12	80	68	338	-190	429	1	2	3	4	5	125	23	93	55	45	103	1332
	135	13	79	69	39	109	-281	147	146	145	144	143	124	24	92	56	44	104	1332
	134	14	78	70	38	110	6	7	8	435	-21	9	123	25	91	57	43	105	1332
	133	15	77	71	37	111	142	141	140	-287	169	139	122	26	90	58	42	106	1332
	132	16	76	72	36	112	438	10	-40	11	12	13	121	27	89	59	41	107	1332
	131	17	75	73	35	113	-290	138	188	137	136	135	-276	424	88	60	40	108	1332
	130	18	74	74	34	114	-232	115	116	117	118	119	120	119	87	61	39	109	1332
	129	19	73	75	35	113	380	33	32	31	30	29	28	29	-124	272	38	110	1332
	128	20	72	76	-12	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	85	37	111	1332
	127	21	73	75	160	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	524	-376	1332
	126	22	736	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	35	1332
	127	21	-588	125	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	113	1332
	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 393, S_{10 \times 10} := 655, S_{14 \times 14} := 917, S_{18 \times 18} := 1179$ and $m := 131$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 444, S_{10 \times 10} := 740, S_{14 \times 14} := 1036, S_{18 \times 18} := 1332$ and $m := 148$.

2.8.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.21. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 18 in flat way is given by*

a81	a82	a83	a84	a85	a86	a87	a88	a89	a90	a91	a92	a93	a94	a95	9*m-a97-a96-a95-a94-a93-a92-a91-a90-a89-a88-a87-a86-a85-a84-a83-a82-a81	a96	a97
m-a81	m-a82	m-a83	m-a84	m-a85	m-a86	m-a87	m-a88	m-a89	m-a90	m-a91	m-a92	m-a93	m-a94	m-a95	a97+a96+a95+a94+a93+a92+a91+a90+a89+a88+a87+a86+a85+a84+a83+a82+a81-8*m	m-a96	m-a97
7*m-a129-a128-a136-a135-a134-a133-a132-a138-a137-a127-a126-a131-a130	a129+a128+a136+a135+a134+a133+a132+a138+a137+a127+a126+a131+a130-6*m															m-a98	a98
a138	m-a138															m-a99	a99
a137	m-a137															m-a100	a100
a136	m-a136															m-a101	a101
a135	m-a135															m-a102	a102
a134	m-a134															m-a103	a103
a133	m-a133															m-a104	a104
a132	m-a132															m-a105	a105
a131	m-a131															m-a106	a106
a130	m-a130															m-a107	a107
a129	m-a129															m-a108	a108
a128	m-a128															m-a109	a109
a127	m-a127															m-a110	a110
a126	m-a126															a98+a99+a110+a106+a107+a108+a109+a102+a103+a104+a105+a100+a101-6*m	7*m-a98-a99-a110-a106-a107-a108-a109-a102-a103-a104-a105-a100-a101
m+a97-a96-a125	m-a125	a82+a112+2*a111+a114+a113+a116+a115+a118+a117+a120+a119+a122+a121+a124+a123+2*a125+a96-a97-8*m-a81	m-a124	m-a123	m-a122	m-a121	m-a120	m-a119	m-a118	m-a117	m-a116	m-a115	m-a114	m-a113	m-a112	m-a111	m+a81-a82-a111
a96+a125-a97	a125	9*m+a81-a82-a112-2*a111-a114-a113-a116-a115-a118-a117-a120-a119-a122-a121-a124-a123-2*a125-a96+a97	a124	a123	a122	a121	a120	a119	a118	a117	a116	a115	a114	a113	a112	a111	a82+a111-a81

The internal part is exactly the same as given in Result 2.15.

• Details

It is an algebraic flat striped magic square of order 18 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×18 and two magic rectangles of order 2×14 embedded with a magic square of order 14. This magic square of order 14 is exactly the same as given in the Result 2.15. In this case the magic sums are $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 9m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.23. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 18 based on Result 2.24 are given by

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	1251												
	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	-262	96	97	1251
	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	401	43	42	1251
	-743	882	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	388	50	51	41	98	1251
	138	1	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	-249	89	88	40	99	1251
	137	2	11	128	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	542	20	21	87	52	39	100	1251
	136	3	80	59	126	125	124	123	122	121	120	-403	119	118	86	53	38	101	1251
	135	4	79	60	237	-98	1	138	4	135	7	132	117	22	85	54	37	102	1251
	134	5	78	61	38	101	2	137	263	-124	8	131	116	23	84	55	36	103	1251
	133	6	77	62	37	102	3	136	5	134	254	-115	115	24	83	56	35	104	1251
	132	7	76	63	36	103	272	-133	6	133	9	130	114	25	82	57	34	105	1251
	131	8	75	64	35	104	131	129	128	-223	127	125	113	26	81	58	33	106	1251
	130	9	74	65	34	105	8	10	11	362	12	14	-158	297	80	59	32	107	1251
	129	10	73	66	107	106	-286	107	108	109	110	111	112	111	79	60	31	108	1251
	128	11	72	67	32	33	425	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	-52	191	30	109	1251
	127	12	69	68	24	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	77	29	110	1251
	126	13	70	71	115	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	518	-379	1251
	15	14	894	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	27	1251
	124	125	-755	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	112	1251
	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/		@IJTANEJA	©IJT	1368									
	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	-145	96	97	1368
	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	297	56	55	1368
	-652	804	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	479	50	51	54	98	1368
	138	14	113	112	111	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	103	-327	102	101	53	99	1368
	137	15	76	76	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	607	20	21	100	52	52	100	1368
	136	16	80	72	139	138	137	136	135	134	133	-455	132	131	99	53	51	101	1368
	135	17	79	73	276	-124	1	151	4	148	7	145	130	22	98	54	50	102	1368
	134	18	78	74	38	114	2	150	289	-137	8	144	129	23	97	55	49	103	1368
	133	19	77	75	37	115	3	149	5	147	280	-128	128	24	96	56	48	104	1368
	132	20	76	76	36	116	298	-146	6	146	9	143	127	25	95	57	47	105	1368
	131	21	75	77	35	117	144	142	141	-249	140	138	126	26	94	58	46	106	1368
	130	22	74	78	34	118	8	10	11	401	12	14	-184	336	93	59	45	107	1368
	129	23	73	79	120	119	-338	120	121	122	123	124	125	124	92	60	44	108	1368
	128	24	72	80	32	33	490	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	-104	256	43	109	1368
	127	25	82	81	-54	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	90	42	110	1368
	126	26	70	71	206	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	440	-288	1368
	28	27	790	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	40	1368
	124	125	-638	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	112	1368
	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 417, S_{10 \times 10} := 695, S_{14 \times 14} := 973, S_{18 \times 18} := 1251$ and $m := 139$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 456, S_{10 \times 10} := 760, S_{14 \times 14} := 1064, S_{18 \times 18} := 1368$ and $m := 152$.

2.8.3 Cornered

Result 2.22. *An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 18 is given by*

																		m-a101	a101	
																			m-a102	a102
																			m-a103	a103
																			m-a104	a104
																			m-a105	a105
																			m-a106	a106
																			m-a107	a107
																			m-a108	a108
																			m-a109	a109
																			m-a110	a110
																			m-a111	a111
																			m-a112	a112
																			m-a113	a113
																			m-a114	a114
																			m-a115	a115
																			a101+a102+a109+a110+a104+a105+a106+a107+a108+a103+a112+a111+a114+a113+a115-7*m	8*m-a101-a102-a109-a110-a104-a105-a106-a107-a108-a103-a112-a111-a114-a113-a115
m+a77-a78+a57-a58+a41-a42-a50+a49-a68+a67-a90+a89+a101-a102-a116	m-a116	m-a117	m-a118	m-a119	m-a120	m-a121	m-a122	m-a123	m-a124	m-a125	m-a126	m-a127	m-a128	m-a129	a78-a57+a58-a41+a42+a50-a49+a68-a67+a90-a89-a101+a102+2*a116+a118+a117+a120+a119+a122+a121+a124+a123+a125-8*m+a129+a128+a127+a126+2*a130-a77	m-a130	m-a130			
a78-a57+a58-a41+a42+a50-a49+a68-a67+a90-a89-a101+a102+a116-a77	a116	a117	a118	a119	a120	a121	a122	a123	a124	a125	a126	a127	a128	a129	a77-a78+a57-a58+a41-a42-a50+a49-a68+a67-a90+a89+a101-a102-2*a116-a118-a117-a120-a119-a122-a121-a124-a123-a125+9*m-a129-a128-a127-a126-2*a130	a130	a130			

The internal part is exactly the same as given in Result 2.19.

• Details

It is an **algebraic cornered striped** magic square of order 18, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 9m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.24. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 18 based on Result 2.25 are given by

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/		https://numbers-magic.com/		@IJTANEJA		©IJT		1179					
	258	1	2	1	5	126	120	11	110	21	96	35	78	53	56	75	30	101	1179
	-127	130	129	130	6	125	119	12	109	22	95	36	77	54	55	76	29	102	1179
	3	4	-1	256	7	124	118	13	108	23	94	37	76	55	54	77	28	103	1179
	128	127	132	-125	244	-113	117	14	107	24	93	38	75	56	53	78	27	104	1179
	381	123	122	-475	121	121	116	15	106	25	92	39	74	57	52	79	26	105	1179
	-250	8	9	606	10	10	-197	328	105	26	91	40	73	58	51	80	25	106	1179
	-246	115	114	113	112	94	111	111	104	27	90	41	72	59	50	81	24	107	1179
	377	16	17	18	19	37	20	20	-225	356	89	42	71	60	49	82	23	108	1179
	100	103	102	101	100	99	98	-242	97	97	88	43	70	61	48	83	22	109	1179
	31	28	29	30	31	32	33	373	34	34	-173	304	69	62	47	84	21	110	1179
	-247	87	86	85	84	83	82	81	80	207	79	79	68	63	46	85	20	111	1179
	378	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-76	52	52	-17	148	45	86	19	112	1179
	62	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	116	57	57	44	87	18	113	1179
	69	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	15	74	74	267	-136	17	114	1179
	-631	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	1167	31	31	16	115	1179
	762	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	-1036	100	100	703	-572	1179
	8	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1050	1	1	1179
	123	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	-919	130	130	1179
	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA		©IJT		1296	
	284	1	2	1	5	139	133	11	123	21	109	35	91	53	69	75	43	101	1296
	-140	143	142	143	6	138	132	12	122	22	108	36	90	54	68	76	42	102	1296
	3	4	-1	282	7	137	131	13	121	23	107	37	89	55	67	77	41	103	1296
	141	140	145	-138	270	-126	130	14	120	24	106	38	88	56	66	78	40	104	1296
	420	136	135	-527	134	134	129	15	119	25	105	39	87	57	65	79	39	105	1296
	-276	8	9	671	10	10	-223	367	118	26	104	40	86	58	64	80	38	106	1296
	-272	128	127	126	125	94	124	124	117	27	103	41	85	59	63	81	37	107	1296
	416	16	17	18	19	50	20	20	-264	408	102	42	84	60	62	82	36	108	1296
	113	116	115	114	113	112	111	-294	110	110	101	43	83	61	61	83	35	109	1296
	31	28	29	30	31	32	33	438	34	34	-225	369	82	62	60	84	34	110	1296
	-286	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	194	92	92	81	63	59	85	33	111	1296
	430	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-50	52	52	-82	226	58	86	32	112	1296
	75	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	38	70	70	57	87	31	113	1296
	69	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	106	74	74	189	-45	30	114	1296
	-735	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	1193	44	44	29	115	1296
	879	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	-1049	100	100	612	-468	1296
	21	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	15	946	14	14	1296
	123	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	-802	130	130	1296
	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 262, S_{6 \times 6} := 393, S_{8 \times 8} := 524, S_{10 \times 10} := 655, S_{12 \times 12} := 786, S_{14 \times 14} := 917, S_{16 \times 16} := 1048, S_{18 \times 18} := 1179$ and $m := 131$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 288, S_{6 \times 6} := 432, S_{8 \times 8} := 576, S_{10 \times 10} := 720, S_{12 \times 12} := 864, S_{14 \times 14} := 1008, S_{16 \times 16} := 1152, S_{18 \times 18} := 1296$ and $m := 144$.

2.9 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 20

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 20, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

2.9.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 2.23. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 20 in cyclic way is given by*

a109	a110	a111	a112	a113	a114	a115	a116	a117	a118	a119	a120	a121	a122	a123	a124	a125	$9m - a109 - a110 - a112 - a111 - a114 - a113 - a116 - a115 - a118 - a117 - a120 - a119 - a122 - a121 - a124 - a123 - a125$	m-a126	a126	
m-a109	m-a110	m-a111	m-a112	m-a113	m-a114	m-a115	m-a116	m-a117	m-a118	m-a119	m-a120	m-a121	m-a122	m-a123	m-a124	m-a125	$a109 + a110 + a112 + a111 + a114 + a113 + a116 + a115 + a118 + a117 + a120 + a119 + a122 + a121 + a124 + a123 + a125 - 8m$	m-a127	a127	
$9m - 2a159 - a160 - a164 - a163 - a162 - a161 - a168 - a167 - a166 - a165 - a173 - a172 - a171 - a170 - a169 - a174 - a127 + a126$	$2a159 + a160 + a164 + a163 + a162 + a161 + a168 + a167 + a166 + a165 + a173 + a172 + a171 + a170 + a169 + a174 + a127 - a126 - 8m$																	m-a128	a128	
a174	m-a174																		m-a129	a129
a173	m-a173																		m-a130	a130
a172	m-a172																		m-a131	a131
a171	m-a171																		m-a132	a132
a170	m-a170																		m-a133	a133
a169	m-a169																		m-a134	a134
a168	m-a168																		m-a135	a135
a167	m-a167																		m-a136	a136
a166	m-a166																		m-a137	a137
a165	m-a165																		m-a138	a138
a164	m-a164																		m-a139	a139
a163	m-a163																		m-a140	a140
a162	m-a162																		m-a141	a141
a161	m-a161																		m-a142	a142
a160	m-a160																	$a140 + a141 + a142 + a139 + a129 + a128 + a136 + a135 + a134 + a133 + a132 + a138 + a137 + a127 + a126 + a131 + a130 - 8m$	$9m - a140 - a141 - a142 - a139 - a129 - a128 - a136 - a135 - a134 - a133 - a132 - a138 - a137 - a127 - a126 - a131 - a130$	
a159	m-a159	$2a143 + a144 + a146 + a145 + a148 + a147 + a150 + a149 + a152 + a151 + a154 + a153 + a156 + a155 - a109 + a110 + a158 + a157 - 8m$	m-a158	m-a157	m-a156	m-a155	m-a154	m-a153	m-a152	m-a151	m-a150	m-a149	m-a148	m-a147	m-a146	m-a145	m-a144	m-a143	m+a109-a110-a143	
a127+a159-a126	m+a126-a127-a159	$9m - 2a143 - a144 - a146 - a145 - a148 - a147 - a150 - a149 - a152 - a151 - a154 - a153 - a156 - a155 + a109 - a110 - a158 - a157$	a158	a157	a156	a155	a154	a153	a152	a151	a150	a149	a148	a147	a146	a145	a144	a143	a110+a143-a109	

The internal part is exactly the same as given in Result 2.17.

● Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic striped** magic square of order 20 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×18 embedded with a magic square of order 16. The internal part, i.e., magic square of order 16 is as given in Result 2.17. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$ and $S_{20 \times 20} := 10m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.25. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 20 based on Result 2.23 are given by

20	mgc	20x20	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	1750													
109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	-414	49	126	1750
66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	589	48	127	1750
-1249	1424	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	380	103	72	47	128	1750
174	1	116	115	114	113	112	111	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	-205	102	73	46	129	1750
173	2	-103	278	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	614	141	34	101	74	45	130	1750
172	3	108	67	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	143	142	-439	140	35	100	75	44	131	1750
171	4	107	68	387	-212	7	8	9	10	11	480	163	12	139	36	99	76	43	132	1750
170	5	106	69	58	117	168	167	166	165	164	-305	162	13	138	37	98	77	42	133	1750
169	6	105	70	57	118	413	-238	346	1	2	1	161	14	137	38	97	78	41	134	1750
168	7	104	71	56	119	24	151	-171	174	173	174	160	15	136	39	96	79	40	135	1750
167	8	103	72	55	120	23	152	3	4	-1	344	159	16	135	40	95	80	39	136	1750
166	9	102	73	54	121	22	153	172	171	176	-169	-280	455	134	41	94	81	38	137	1750
165	10	101	74	53	122	21	154	-258	155	156	157	158	157	133	42	93	82	37	138	1750
164	11	100	75	52	123	22	153	433	20	19	18	17	18	-358	533	92	83	36	139	1750
163	12	99	76	51	124	-284	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	132	131	91	84	35	140	1750
162	13	98	77	52	123	459	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	44	-36	211	34	141	1750
161	14	97	78	122	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	89	33	142	1750
160	15	98	77	53	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	86	878	-703	1750
159	16	1152	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	31	1750
160	15	-977	158	157	156	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	143	144	1750
1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750	1750

20	mgc	20x20	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	1860													
109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	-315	60	126	1860
77	76	75	74	73	72	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	501	59	127	1860
-1150	1336	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	457	114	72	58	128	1860
174	12	127	126	125	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	-271	113	73	57	129	1860
173	13	-26	212	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	669	152	34	112	74	56	130	1860
172	14	108	78	161	160	159	158	157	156	155	154	153	-483	151	35	111	75	55	131	1860
171	15	107	79	442	-256	7	8	9	10	11	513	174	12	150	36	110	76	54	132	1860
170	16	106	80	58	128	179	178	177	176	175	-327	173	13	149	37	109	77	53	133	1860
169	17	105	81	57	129	446	-260	368	1	2	1	172	14	148	38	108	78	52	134	1860
168	18	104	82	56	130	24	162	-182	185	184	185	171	15	147	39	107	79	51	135	1860
167	19	103	83	55	131	23	163	3	4	-1	366	170	16	146	40	106	80	50	136	1860
166	20	102	84	54	132	22	164	183	182	187	-180	-302	488	145	41	105	81	49	137	1860
165	21	101	85	53	133	21	165	-280	166	167	168	169	168	144	42	104	82	48	138	1860
164	22	100	86	52	134	22	164	466	20	19	18	17	18	-402	588	103	83	47	139	1860
163	23	99	87	51	135	-328	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143	142	102	84	46	140	1860
162	24	98	88	52	134	514	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	44	-102	288	45	141	1860
161	25	97	89	56	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	100	101	100	44	142	1860
160	26	98	88	130	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	86	790	-604	1860
159	27	1064	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	42	1860
160	26	-878	158	157	156	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	143	144	1860
1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860	1860

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 350, S_{8 \times 8} := 700, S_{12 \times 12} := 1050, S_{16 \times 16} := 1400, S_{20 \times 20} := 1750$ and $m := 175$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 372, S_{8 \times 8} := 744, S_{12 \times 12} := 1116, S_{16 \times 16} := 1488, S_{20 \times 20} := 1860$ and $m := 186$.

2.9.2 Flat-Type

Result 2.24. An algebraic striped magic square of order 20 in flat way is given by

a106	a107	a108	a109	a110	a111	a112	a113	a114	a115	a116	a117	a118	a119	a120	a121	a122	$10*m-a123-a124-a122-a120-a121-a118-a119-a116-a117-a115-a113-a114-a111-a112-a109-a110-a107-a108-a106$	a123	a124
m-a106	m-a107	m-a108	m-a109	m-a110	m-a111	m-a112	m-a113	m-a114	m-a115	m-a116	m-a117	m-a118	m-a119	m-a120	m-a121	m-a122	$a123+a124+a122+a120+a121+a118+a119+a116+a117+a115+a113+a114+a111+a112+a109+a110+a107+a108+a106-9*m$	m-a123	m-a124
$8*m-a161-a160-a159-a158-a157-a165-a164-a163-a162-a170-a169-a168-a167-a166-a171$	$a161+a160+a159+a158+a157+a165+a164+a163+a162+a170+a169+a168+a167+a166+a171-7*m$																	m-a125	a125
a171	m-a171																	m-a126	a126
a170	m-a170																	m-a127	a127
a169	m-a169																	m-a128	a128
a168	m-a168																	m-a129	a129
a167	m-a167																	m-a130	a130
a166	m-a166																	m-a131	a131
a165	m-a165																	m-a132	a132
a164	m-a164																	m-a133	a133
a163	m-a163																	m-a134	a134
a162	m-a162																	m-a135	a135
a161	m-a161																	m-a136	a136
a160	m-a160																	m-a137	a137
a159	m-a159																	m-a138	a138
a158	m-a158																	m-a139	a139
a157	m-a157																	$a139+a134+a135+a136+a137+a138+a130+a131+a132+a133+a125+a126+a127+a128+a129-7*m$	$8*m-a139-a134-a135-a136-a137-a138-a130-a131-a132-a133-a125-a126-a127-a128-a129$
m+a124-a123-a156	m-a156	$a151+a153+a152+a155+a154+2*a140+a123-a124+2*a156+a107-a106+a142+a141+a144+a143+a146+a145+a148+a147+a150+a149-9*m$	m-a155	m-a154	m-a153	m-a152	m-a151	m-a150	m-a149	m-a148	m-a147	m-a146	m-a145	m-a144	m-a143	m-a142	m-a141	m-a140	m+a106-a107-a140
a123+a156-a124	a156	$10*m-a151-a153-a152-a155-a154-2*a140-a123-a124-2*a156-a107+a106-a142-a141-a144-a143-a146-a145-a148-a147-a150-a149$	a155	a154	a153	a152	a151	a150	a149	a148	a147	a146	a145	a144	a143	a142	a141	a140	a107+a140-a106

The internal part is exactly the same as given in Result 2.18.

• Details

It is an **algebraic flat striped** magic square of order 20 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×20 and two magic rectangles of order 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 16. This magic square of order 16 is exactly, the same as given in Result 2.18. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$ and $S_{20 \times 20} := 10m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.26. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 20 based on Result 2.24 are given by

20	mgc	20x20 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																		1720	
	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	-465	123	124	1720
	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	637	49	48	1720
	-1084	1256	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	418	69	70	47	125	1720
	171	1	115	114	113	112	111	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	103	-246	103	102	46	126	1720
	170	2	-68	240	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	724	32	33	101	71	45	127	1720
	169	3	105	67	149	148	147	146	145	144	143	142	141	-552	140	139	100	72	44	128	1720
	168	4	104	68	317	-145	5	6	7	8	9	632	10	11	138	34	99	73	43	129	1720
	167	5	103	69	56	116	167	166	165	164	163	-460	162	161	137	35	98	74	42	130	1720
	166	6	102	70	55	117	281	-109	340	1	2	1	160	12	136	36	97	75	41	131	1720
	165	7	101	71	54	118	22	150	-168	171	170	171	159	13	135	37	96	76	40	132	1720
	164	8	100	72	53	119	21	151	3	4	-1	338	158	14	134	38	95	77	39	133	1720
	163	9	99	73	52	120	20	152	169	168	173	-166	-133	305	133	39	94	78	38	134	1720
	162	10	98	74	51	121	20	19	569	18	17	16	15	14	132	40	93	79	37	135	1720
	161	11	97	75	50	122	152	153	-397	154	155	156	157	158	-257	429	92	80	36	136	1720
	160	12	96	76	124	123	-365	124	125	126	127	128	129	130	131	130	91	81	35	137	1720
	159	13	95	77	48	49	537	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	42	-24	196	34	138	1720
	158	14	79	78	116	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	89	33	139	1720
	157	15	93	94	56	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	84	83	82	83	776	-604	1720
	17	16	1264	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	31	1720
	155	156	-1092	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	143	142	141	140	141	1720
	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720	1720

20	mgc	20x20 Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																		1810
106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	-375	123	124	1810
75	74	73	72	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	556	58	57	1810
-1012	1193	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	490	69	70	56	125	1810
171	10	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	-309	112	111	55	126	1810
170	11	-14	195	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	778	32	33	110	71	54	127	1810
169	12	105	76	158	157	156	155	154	153	152	151	150	-597	149	148	109	72	53	128	1810
168	13	104	77	353	-172	5	6	7	8	9	668	10	11	147	34	108	73	52	129	1810
167	14	103	78	56	125	176	175	174	173	172	-487	171	170	146	35	107	74	51	130	1810
166	15	102	79	55	126	299	-118	358	1	2	1	169	12	145	36	106	75	50	131	1810
165	16	101	80	54	127	22	159	-177	180	179	180	168	13	144	37	105	76	49	132	1810
164	17	100	81	53	128	21	160	3	4	-1	356	167	14	143	38	104	77	48	133	1810
163	18	99	82	52	129	20	161	178	177	182	-175	-142	323	142	39	103	78	47	134	1810
162	19	98	83	51	130	20	19	605	18	17	16	15	14	141	40	102	79	46	135	1810
161	20	97	84	50	131	161	162	-424	163	164	165	166	167	-284	465	101	80	45	136	1810
160	21	96	85	133	132	-410	133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	139	100	81	44	137	1810
159	22	95	86	48	49	591	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	42	-69	250	43	138	1810
158	23	88	87	53	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	98	42	139	1810
157	24	93	94	128	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	84	83	82	83	713	-532	1810
26	25	1183	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	40	1810
155	156	-1002	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	143	142	141	140	141	1810
1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810	1810

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) *First Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 344, S_{8 \times 8} := 688, S_{12 \times 12} := 1032, S_{16 \times 16} := 1204, S_{20 \times 20} := 1720$ and $m := 172$.
- (ii) *Second Example:* $S_{4 \times 4} := 362, S_{8 \times 8} := 724, S_{12 \times 12} := 1086, S_{16 \times 16} := 1448, S_{20 \times 20} := 1810$ and $m := 181$.

2.9.3 Cornered

Result 2.25. An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 20 is given by

																			m-a131	a131
																			m-a132	a132
																			m-a133	a133
																			m-a134	a134
																			m-a135	a135
																			m-a136	a136
																			m-a137	a137
																			m-a138	a138
																			m-a139	a139
																			m-a140	a140
																			m-a141	a141
																			m-a142	a142
																			m-a143	a143
																			m-a144	a144
																			m-a145	a145
																			m-a146	a146
																			m-a147	a147
																			a139+a140+a134+a135+a136+a137+a138+a131+a132+a133+a142+a141+a144+a143+a146+a145+a147-8*m	9*m-a139-a140-a134-a135-a136-a137-a138-a131-a132-a133-a142-a141-a144-a143-a146-a145-a147
a38+a39+a40+a41+a36+a37-a60+2*a43-a80+a59+a79-a104+a103+a131-a132+a35-a92+a91+a69-a70-a47+a51+a42-4*m-a118+a117-a148	m-a148	m-a149	m-a150	m-a151	m-a152	m-a153	m-a154	m-a155	m-a156	m-a157	m-a158	m-a159	m-a160	m-a161	m-a162	m-a163		a60-2*a43+a80-a59-a79+a104-a103+a151+a153+a152+a155+a154-a131+a132-a35+a92-a91-a69+a70+a47-a51-a42+a156-4*m+a118-a117+a161+a160+a159+a158+a157+2*a164+a163+a162+2*a148+a150+a149-a38-a39-a40-a41-a36-a37	m-a164	m-a164
a60-2*a43+a80-a59-a79+a104-a103-a131+a132-a35+a92-a91-a69+a70+a47-a51-a42+5*m+a118-a117+a148-a38-a39-a40-a41-a36-a37	a148	a149	a150	a151	a152	a153	a154	a155	a156	a157	a158	a159	a160	a161	a162	a163		a38+a39+a40+a41+a36+a37-a60+2*a43-a80+a59+a79-a104+a103-a151-a153-a152-a155-a154+a131-a132+a35-a92+a91+a69-a70-a47+a51+a42-a156+5*m-a118+a117-a161-a160-a159-a158-a157-2*a164-a163-a162-2*a148-a150-a149	a164	a164

The internal part is exactly the same as given in Result ??.

● Details

It is an **algebraic cornered striped** magic square of order 20, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16 and 18 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 9m$ and $S_{20 \times 20} := 10m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 2.27. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 20 based on Result 2.25 are given by

20	mgc	20x20	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	1650				
	326	1 2 1	5 160	154 11	144 21	130 35	112 53	90 75	64 101	34 131	1650
	-161	164 163 164	6 159	153 12	143 22	129 36	111 54	89 76	63 102	33 132	1650
	3	4 -1 324	7 158	152 13	142 23	128 37	110 55	88 77	62 103	32 133	1650
	162	161 166 -159	312 -147	151 14	141 24	127 38	109 56	87 78	61 104	31 134	1650
	483	157 156 -611	155 155	150 15	140 25	126 39	108 57	86 79	60 105	30 135	1650
	-318	8 9 776	10 10	-265 430	139 26	125 40	107 58	85 80	59 106	29 136	1650
	-314	149 148 147	146 94	145 145	138 27	124 41	106 59	84 81	58 107	28 137	1650
	479	16 17 18	19 71	20 20	-327 492	123 42	105 60	83 82	57 108	27 138	1650
	134	137 136 135	134 133	132 -378	131 131	122 43	104 61	82 83	56 109	26 139	1650
	31	28 29 30	31 32	33 543	34 34	-309 474	103 62	81 84	55 110	25 140	1650
	-349	121 173 119	120 117	116 115	114 118	113 113	102 63	80 85	54 111	24 141	1650
	514	44 -8 46	45 48	49 50	51 47	52 52	-187 352	79 86	53 112	23 142	1650
	43	101 100 99	98 97	96 95	94 93	92 -35	91 91	78 87	52 113	22 143	1650
	122	64 65 66	67 68	69 70	71 72	73 200	74 74	63 102	51 114	21 144	1650
	-903	77 76 75	74 73	72 71	70 69	68 67	66 1235	65 65	50 115	20 145	1650
	1068	88 89 90	91 92	93 94	95 96	97 98	99 -1070	100 100	465 -300	19 146	1650
	42	49 48 47	46 45	44 43	42 41	40 39	38 37	36 778	35 35	18 147	1650
	123	116 117 118	119 120	121 122	123 124	125 126	127 128	129 -613	130 130	1043 -878	1650
	-417	17 16 15	14 13	12 11	10 9	8 7	6 5	4 3	2 1913	1 1	1650
	582	148 149 150	151 152	153 154	155 156	157 158	159 160	161 162	163 -1748	164 164	1650
	1650	1650 1650 1650	1650 1650	1650 1650	1650 1650	1650 1650	1650 1650	1650 1650	1650 1650	1650 1650	1650

20	mgc	20x20	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	1710				
	338	1 2 1	5 166	160 11	150 21	136 35	118 53	96 75	70 101	40 131	1710
	-167	170 169 170	6 165	159 12	149 22	135 36	117 54	95 76	69 102	39 132	1710
	3	4 -1 336	7 164	158 13	148 23	134 37	116 55	94 77	68 103	38 133	1710
	168	167 172 -165	324 -153	157 14	147 24	133 38	115 56	93 78	67 104	37 134	1710
	501	163 162 -635	161 161	156 15	146 25	132 39	114 57	92 79	66 105	36 135	1710
	-330	8 9 806	10 10	-277 448	145 26	131 40	113 58	91 80	65 106	35 136	1710
	-326	155 154 153	152 94	151 151	144 27	130 41	112 59	90 81	64 107	34 137	1710
	497	16 17 18	19 77	20 20	-345 516	129 42	111 60	89 82	63 108	33 138	1710
	140	143 142 141	140 139	138 -402	137 137	128 43	110 61	88 83	62 109	32 139	1710
	31	28 29 30	31 32	33 573	34 34	-333 504	109 62	87 84	61 110	31 140	1710
	-367	127 167 125	126 123	122 121	120 124	119 119	108 63	86 85	60 111	30 141	1710
	538	44 4 46	45 48	49 50	51 47	52 52	-217 388	85 86	59 112	29 142	1710
	61	107 106 105	104 103	102 101	100 99	98 -83	97 97	84 87	58 113	28 143	1710
	110	64 65 66	67 68	69 70	71 72	73 254	74 74	27 144	57 114	27 144	1710
	-951	83 82 81	80 79	78 77	76 75	74 73	72 1247	71 71	56 115	26 145	1710
	1122	88 89 90	91 92	93 94	95 96	97 98	99 -1076	100 100	423 -252	25 146	1710
	48	55 54 53	52 51	50 49	48 47	46 45	44 43	42 730	41 41	24 147	1710
	123	116 117 118	119 120	121 122	123 124	125 126	127 128	129 -559	130 130	995 -824	1710
	-441	23 22 21	20 19	18 17	16 15	14 13	12 11	10 9	8 1889	7 7	1710
	612	148 149 150	151 152	153 154	155 156	157 158	159 160	161 162	163 -1718	164 164	1710
	1710	1710 1710 1710	1710 1710	1710 1710	1710 1710	1710 1710	1710 1710	1710 1710	1710 1710	1710 1710	1710

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) **First Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 330, S_{6 \times 6} := 495, S_{8 \times 8} := 660, S_{10 \times 10} := 825, S_{12 \times 12} := 990, S_{14 \times 14} := 1155, S_{16 \times 16} := 1320, S_{18 \times 18} := 1485, S_{20 \times 20} := 1650$ and $m := 165$.
- (ii) **Second Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 342, S_{6 \times 6} := 513, S_{8 \times 8} := 684, S_{10 \times 10} := 855, S_{12 \times 12} := 1026, S_{14 \times 14} := 1197, S_{16 \times 16} := 1368, S_{18 \times 18} := 1539, S_{20 \times 20} := 1710$ and $m := 171$.

3 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares,**
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers,**
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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 - [3] **F. Gaspalou**, "Magic Squares" <http://www.gaspalou.fr/magic-squares/>
 - [4] **W. Trump**, <http://www.trump.de/magic-squares>
 - [5] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
 - [6] **W.S. Andrews**, Magic squares and Cubes, Dover Publications, New York
- Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares: Dates and Days of the Year**
- [7] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7 Representing Dates and Days of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 04, 2025, pp. 1-474, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15338142>.
 - [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 8 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 04, 2025, pp. 1-134, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15338246>.
 - [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 9 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 09, 2025, pp. 1-132, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15375349>.
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 - [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of order 12 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, June 10, 2025, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15631884>.
- Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares: Different Styles**
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reduced Entries Magic and Semi-Magic Squares of Orders 3, 5, 7 and 9, **Zenodo**, July 01, 2025, pp. 1-65, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15783321>.
 - [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reduced Entries Magic and Semi-Magic Squares of Orders 4, 6, 8 and 10, **Zenodo**, July 05, 2025, pp. 1-85, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15814675>.

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• Double-Digit Magic Squares

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